

Norwich Institute
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The business case for grasspea in Ethiopia

An action plan to provide Ethiopian farmers with a safe,
nutritious and climate-smart protein source.

September 2025 | Matt Heaton & Hileena Chole

Executive summary

This document provides an overview and action plan for the scale-up and use of low-ODAP grasspea across Ethiopia to complement nutritious and resilient climate-smart agriculture. Grasspea has a long history in Ethiopia as one of the most widely cultivated legumes, yet it remains underutilised and marginal within formal seed systems and value chains. The presence of the neurotoxin β -ODAP in traditional varieties has discouraged widespread consumption and investment, despite the crop's adaptability, regenerative qualities, and importance to smallholder farmers.

Recent advances in bioscience have enabled more targeted and rapid breeding progress, resulting in low-ODAP varieties with improved agronomic performance. These developments offer an opportunity to realise the full potential of grasspea for Ethiopian farming systems, particularly in areas prone to climate stress. However, questions remain about how to ensure that improved grasspea seed reaches farmers at scale, in ways that are timely, inclusive, and sustainable.

In this document, we present a synthesis of recent developments in grasspea research and use this to outline three action plans for the expansion of improved grasspea use in Ethiopia. One approach follows the traditional Ethiopian model of government seed purchase and distribution. A second outlines how integrated seed systems involving local seed businesses (LSBs) and farmer organisations could support a more decentralised and sustainable model of seed delivery. A third, phased approach combines the strengths of the previous two and offers a pathway for both immediate and longer-term uptake. Each approach is described with reference to its actor landscape, implementation considerations, and embedded theory of change.

We argue that while the phased approach may provide a pragmatic starting point for rapid expansion, it is the integrated seed system model that holds the greatest potential for sustained delivery of improved grasspea across Ethiopia's diverse farming landscapes. We conclude with a set of recommendations for the partnerships, capacities, and enabling conditions needed to ensure that improved grasspea can contribute meaningfully to food and nutrition security, climate resilience, and rural livelihoods.

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Acronyms

β -ODAP - β -N-oxalyl-L- α , β -diaminopropionic acid, the compound in grasspea that can be toxic under high and sustained consumption.

DA - Development Agent

EAA - Ethiopian Agricultural Authority

EIAR - Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research

EOSA - Ethio-Organic Seed Action

ESP - Ethiopian Seed Partnership (previously the Ethiopian Netherlands Seed Partnership)

ESE - Ethiopian Seed Enterprise

ICARDA - International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas

JIC - John Innes Centre

MoA - Ministry of Agriculture

NISD - Norwich Institute for Sustainable Development

QDS - Quality Declared Seed

RARI - Regional Agricultural Research Institute

RBoA - Regional Bureau of Agriculture

RSE - Regional Seed Enterprise

WBoA - Woreda Bureau of Agriculture

Introduction

Grasspea (*Lathyrus sativus*) is a resilient and nutritious crop with huge potential for regenerative and climate-smart agriculture. Yet despite the potential of grasspea and the development of improved varieties, more can be done to bring these varieties to farmers. Doing so offers potentially millions of farmers worldwide with a more resilient, nutritious and regenerative crop to improve local food and biodiversity security despite changing climates.

This document provides the business case and implementation plan to bring improved grasspea varieties to Ethiopian farmers. Based on the culmination of previous and ongoing transdisciplinary research, we synthesise the available data on grasspea improvement and provide three business case mechanisms of how to enable widespread

adoption of improved grasspea in Ethiopia. Doing so seeks to inform ongoing implementation plans for uptake of improved grasspea in Ethiopia, and as a case study for this same adoption more globally.

This document starts with the background context on grasspea with an overview on its history, cultivation, traits and the recent scientific developments working to realise the potential of the crop. We follow this general introduction with a focus on grasspea use in Ethiopia and its potential in local agriculture. We then share three business scenarios, with an approach overview, actor populated theory of change and implementation plan. We conclude with recommendations based on what we believe to be the best way forward from these business case scenarios.

Grasspea cultivation

Grasspea is a legume of the Fabaceae family (peas and beans), which grows as an annual herbaceous plant which grows between 30-90cm tall. It produces tendrils, blue, white or pink flowers and flattened pods with several seeds. These peas are flat, angular and range in colour from pale cream to dark brown.

Grasspea is one of the oldest cultivated legumes, first cultivated around 8,000 BCE in the Eastern Mediterranean and fertile Crescent (Sarkar et al. 2019). As such, it has a long history of human cultivation across Europe, Southern Asia and Ethiopia. Today, grasspea is still widely grown for consumption across Bangladesh, Ethiopia, India, Nepal, Spain, Turkey, and Syria. Grasspea has also

been cultivated for fodder and feed in Egypt, Morocco, Algeria, Libya, Iraq, Iran, Afghanistan, Syria, Lebanon, Portugal, Spain, and Italy. Estimating grasspea yields is challenging across many of these areas as it is often left out of official reports in favour of more major legumes. Yields however generally vary across these areas depending on the growing conditions, between 400-1000 kg per hectare, and cultivation is thought to be increasing in South Asia and Ethiopia (Heaton, 2023).

One of the reasons that grasspea is widely grown is due to its nature as one of the most climate resilient legumes. It can survive droughts or floods where other legumes would perish and provides a harvest

on marginal and arid lands. Grasspea also shows reasonable salinity tolerance, has generally good pest resilience and, due to its nature as a legume, is able to grow well in low-nitrogen soils, while also improving soil fertility. Grasspea therefore provides a dependable crop in challenging growing conditions and also performs well as a relay crop, surviving off the residual soil moisture at the end of the growing season.¹ For instance, South Asian farmers use grasspea as a relay crop with rice, broadcasting the seed across rain-fed paddies during the end of the rice growing season, later harvesting the grasspea that survives on the residual soil moisture. This form of cultivation is also believed to fertilise the paddies through nitrogen-fixation associated with the legume. Grasspea is therefore often chosen by resource-poor farmers to grow alongside their main crop or as an insurance crop to yield a harvest despite weather shocks.

In addition to climate resilience, grasspea is also valued for its nutritional content. The seeds have a protein content of approximately 30% of dry matter, higher than comparable cool season legumes, lentil, chickpea and pea (Sani et al., 2024). Similarly to other legumes, this protein composition is high in lysine, but low in sulphur-containing amino acids, cysteine and methionine. This makes grasspea an ideal protein balance to cereals, which offer higher amounts of sulphur-containing amino acids, but lower lysine levels. Grasspea also offers a source of micronutrients such as magnesium, iron and

potassium, as well as a source of dietary fibre and carbohydrates.

Combined, these nutritional qualities mean grasspea offers a valuable source of nutrition to populations in low input and harsher agricultural environments. These nutritional benefits also apply to livestock, where grasspea green fodder contains around 18-20% protein, good sources of micronutrients and moderate to high digestibility (Lambein et al., 2019). Grasspea dry straw contains lower levels of these qualities, but remains comparable or better than cereal straws. Subsequently grasspea is commonly fed to ruminants across South Asia and Ethiopia.

For these reasons, grasspea has become a widely cultivated crop for farmers to achieve reliable and nutritious harvests. These same qualities mean that many are looking to the potential of grasspea for wider use as part of climate adaptation strategies, to support both arable and livestock farming. The high protein content of grasspea means that it is also being considered by European countries as a protein source to replace soy in livestock feed, or as an alternative protein source as societies shift from animal protein sources (Heaton 2023). But grasspea also brings several challenges that have traditionally limited the spread of grasspea cultivation. In this next section we explore these challenges, and why recent developments around research and collaboration suggest now is the time for grasspea extension planning.

Figure 1: Grasspea cultivation across the world.

1. This practice is also believed to fertilise the paddies for the following rice season on account of grasspea being a legume and able to fix nitrogen.

Grasspea research targets and developments

Despite a long history of cultivation, grasspea is considered an ‘underutilised crop’ having received limited attention from modern crop breeding efforts, compared to the global ‘major crops’ of cereals and high-value vegetables. This lack of breeding work on grasspea means that, while it offers innate beneficial traits, there remain clear breeding targets for improvement. Some of these targets have become much more accessible through recent bioscience breakthroughs.

The most widely reported challenge with grasspea is the presence of a neurotoxin, β -N-oxalyl-L- α,β -diaminopropionic acid (β -ODAP), present within all parts of the plant. β -ODAP is safe to eat as part of a balanced diet, but where grasspea is consumed as the dominant part of the diet for three or more months, can cause fairly quick onset of irreversible paralysis of the legs, a condition known as neurolathyrism (Rao et al., 1964; Enneking 2011). This toxicity is offset when ODAP is consumed in the presence of foods rich in methionine or cysteine, such as cereals, or high in antioxidants (Khandare et al. 2018; Lambein et al. 2019; Saligame 2011; Vaz Patto and Rubiales 2014). As such grasspea is regularly consumed safely by many globally, including daily or more in parts of Ethiopia (Heaton et al. 2025). The challenge is that grasspea’s resilience raises the likelihood of it being one of the remaining crops during weather shocks, increasing the likelihood of local populations relying on it for extended periods of time and raising the potential of developing neurolathyrism. Further, it seems that ODAP levels in grasspea increase under stress conditions, and that the processing methods of removing ODAP (soaking and extended cooking) would become more challenging under times of water shortage (Girma et al., 2011). These processing methods are also incomplete, leaving some ODAP in the plant, leading to further uncertainty around how much ODAP is being consumed.

Over-reliance of grasspea has historically caused outbreaks of neurolathyrism, causing some countries to ban the crop (Getahun et al. 1999; Singh and Rao 2013). For instance, the sale of grasspea was banned in India in 1961 although some states have recently lifted the ban due to growing local consumption without neurolathyrism outbreaks.³

Making a ‘safe’ grasspea variety is however not a straightforward target. The first challenge is that there is no defined threshold for safe ODAP content. Another issue is that the level of ODAP in the plant is variable, influenced by environmental contexts, for instance increasing under drought conditions (Girma and Korbu 2012). Still, grasspea genetics are the fundamental driver of ODAP levels and so the delivery of low or zero ODAP lines has remained a major target for grasspea research. Multiple research groups have worked on delivering a low ODAP grasspea through selective breeding from the global diversity of grasspea accessions, 4,400 lines of which are based at the International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA) (Heaton 2023). Most of the low-ODAP varieties that have been released came from NARS research, some, notably the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI) and Ethiopian Institute for Agricultural Research (EIAR).

The ICAR system produced a low-ODAP variety with the Indian Agricultural Research Institute’s ‘Pusa-24’, a selection identified in 1966 and released 1973-74, with ~0.2% ODAP. ‘Pusa-24’ became a founder parent for later low-ODAP cultivars. Subsequent research with ICAR-IIPR Kanpur and AICRP partner centres used conventional crossing and selection (often with Pusa-24 ancestry) to combine low seed ODAP with yield and adaptation (such as ‘Ratan’ Bio L-212, ‘Prateek’ LS 157-14 and ‘Mahateora’ RLS 4595). The availability of these low-toxin cultivars underpinned Indian regulatory re-assessments; by 2016, national authorities moved toward lifting legacy bans on

2. Also referred to as ‘opportunity’ or ‘orphan’ crops.

3. Grasspea cultivation continues to rise in response to farmer use across India despite the ban, with current coverage estimated at 400,000 hectares.

khesari dal sale/consumption (subject to conditions)—explicitly crediting ICAR/ICMR evidence on low-ODAP varieties.

BARI released BARI Khesari-1 and BARI Khesari-2 in the mid-1990s as the institute's first low- β -ODAP cultivars (<0.10% β -ODAP) through conventional crossing and selection using local high-yielding backgrounds and low-neurotoxin donors (some originating from IARI/ICARDA pipelines) (Arora *et al.*, 1996). Through collaboration with ICARDA through the 2010s, BARI produced BARI Khesari-3 (reported as an ICARDA line, <0.1% β -ODAP) and BARI Khesari-4 (released ~2013). In 2024, BARI scientists worked with ICARDA in farmer dialogues in Bangladesh's char areas to address lingering stigma around khesari and to position low-ODAP cultivars as climate-resilient, nitrogen-fixing options in pulse-deficit systems.

EIAR began grasspea improvement in the 1960s at the Holetta and Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Centre, which was later complemented by a partnership with ICARDA to funnel low-toxin, high-yielding genotypes into national testing. The work combined multi-location, multi-season evaluation with agronomic recommendations (e.g. earlier planting) to reduce ODAP expression. In 2005, 'Wasié' Ethiopia's first "safe" grasspea variety was released, with around <0.1% ODAP at release and recommended with early sowing to help keep ODAP low (Girma and Korbu 2012; Kumar *et al.* 2021).

More recently, researchers from the John Innes Centre have created additional low-ODAP lines by mutagenesis, and are investigating the genetic basis of this trait to broaden the gene-pool of available low-ODAP material and allow for faster breeding of this trait into locally adapted varieties.

Reductions in ODAP alone however are unlikely to result in widespread adoption. For instance, Norwich Institute for Sustainable Development (NISD) research in Ethiopia shows that farmers want low ODAP varieties, but are more interested in other traits from improvement (Heaton *et al.* 2025). This provides a reminder that toxicity is but one trait and although it has dominated the narrative around grasspea, there are other agronomic improvements that would benefit grasspea production. The overwhelming focus on ODAP may therefore have caused many other agronomic traits to be overlooked for improvement as part of modern breeding programmes (Kumar *et al.* 2021; Heaton 2023; Heaton *et al.* 2025). These might include.

- **Yield:** pod number, seeds per pod, larger seeds and biomass.
- **Abiotic resistance:** resistance to droughts, floods and salinity.
- **Biotic resistance:** resistance to specific pests and diseases such as aphids, Orobanche and powdery mildew.
- **Growing and harvesting:** plants that grow more favourably together, reduce harvest loss factors like pod shatter or increase the ease of mechanised farming.
- **Nutritional and processing:** increased protein or nutrient content, improved bioavailability, reduced cooking time and better taste qualities.

It is these agronomic traits that could make grasspea more productive, nutritious and profitable, and ultimately encourage more commercial and mechanised farmers to adopt the crop over alternatives such as chickpea or lentils. Another point for consideration is that these traits are specific across locations and demographics, increasing the need for farmer and consumer engagement for trait targeting (Heaton *et al.* 2025). There is, therefore, a need to build greater engagement with farmers to understand local grasspea improvement targets, and to combine these with breeding programmes to introgress these qualities into improved varieties.

This latter area is also one where recent research developments have accelerated the

pathway to bringing improved varieties to farmers' fields. Until recently, a major challenge for grasspea breeding efforts was the absence of a genome sequence assembly, but multiple assemblies have since been released, the most recent and highest quality of these coming from the John Innes Centre in 2024 (Vigouroux et al. 2024). These assemblies not only pave the way for more informed breeding choices, they open up more opportunities to use more advanced precision breeding approaches. New advances in speed breeding facilities at ICARDA and the John Innes Centre also mean that trait introgression can take place in a fraction of the time. All of these natural science developments mean that improved grasspea varieties are already being created and have the potential to further improve in the near future.

A final research area concerns social reasons related to grasspea adoption decisions. For instance, in areas where there have been neurological outbreaks or bans around grasspea use, there may be cultural concerns about the safety of the crop. Similarly, in some areas, there are social stigmas that relate grasspea as a food of the poor. These views inhibit the adoption of grasspea, how open farmers and food retailers are to publicising their use of grasspea and the relative market demand. Yet improved grasspea could offer many benefits to these same populations. Social science research can therefore understand these social dimensions to the acceptability of improved grasspea, to guide the sensitisation, delivery and adoption of improved varieties.

Current status of grasspea use in Ethiopia

This section focuses on a synthesis of context, research and developments related to grasspea use in Ethiopia. Here we explore how grasspea demand is increasing and why this raises the need to bring safer and more productive grasspea varieties into circulation.

Grasspea, known as *guaya* in Amharic, has long been a part of Ethiopian agriculture, and particularly as a valuable protein source in harsh growing conditions. It is mostly cultivated across the central and northern highland areas of Amhara, Oromia and Tigray. Grasspea is mostly cultivated by smallholders and is more prevalent in areas of less fertile soils, or in water scarce areas which are vulnerable to drought. Farmers might also plant grasspea in foothill areas below sloped areas where its flood tolerance means it can withstand flood waters that run downhill.

The main market alternatives to grasspea are chickpea, lentil and faba bean which are all

The above research areas demonstrate the need for close collaboration across disciplines. The grasspea research community has long been a collaborative one, with engagement being clustered around mutual regional interest (e.g. South Asian collaborations on account of similar breeding objectives) or through personal links between researchers with a shared interest. Recent years have seen a particular push to create shared platforms and research networks to strategically unite the grasspea field. For instance, the Germinate grasspea database provides an open database of genetic and phenotypic information for researchers. Similarly grasspea.net provides a central website for grasspea resources and The Lambein Fund provides a newsletter and travel funding for grasspea events. These groups not only connect researchers, they accelerate the sharing of resources and reduce the chance of time lost in duplication of efforts. Central to these networks are the John Innes Centre for their lab research on grasspea, ICARDA as the host of the largest global diversity collection of grasspea and The James Hutton institute for their open sharing of data. Grasspea also features in the Crop Trust BOLD crop selection, as well as a priority crop under the FAO Vision for Adapted Crops and Soils (VACS) initiative. The VACS initiative targets the use of key opportunity crops to build climate resilience, providing a spotlight and funding for grasspea use for climate adaptation. Overall, the need for climate smart crops, the latest research outputs around grasspea breeding and the growing community creates a space for a wealth of advances in grasspea research.

commonly grown in similar areas. These alternatives have a long history of improvement by the Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) and ICARDA, with many improved varieties available for farmers to access from formal seed sellers, regional or district enterprises and farmer cooperative groups. Demand for these alternatives has become increasingly commercialised and includes both national (including rural to urban transport) and export markets. All of these alternatives offer more varietal options, plurality in seed sources and more established value chains than grasspea. Grasspea cultivation areas and harvest are however rising in Ethiopia and many are changing to the crop for its dependable yields despite seasonal variability. Previous NISD research finds that grasspea is gaining popularity in growing areas due to its reliability but also its taste and cooking quality of thickening sauces (Figure 2, Heaton et al. 2025). This rise in cultivation is also driven by farmer shifts to grasspea, away from other legumes that are struggling with losses from pest pressures.

Figure 2: Grasspea cultivation is increasing across Ethiopia, adapted from (Heaton et al. 2025)

As confirmed by recent NISD research, grasspea is regularly eaten across these areas in a range of dishes (Heaton et al. 2025). These include as part of *shiro* or *wot* dishes (spicy Ethiopian stews), boiled as beans for *nifro* or roasted as the snack *kollo* (Barpete et al. 2021). More rarely grasspea might be consumed as flour mixed into bread, or as the vegan cream alternative *hilbet*.⁴ This range of dishes covers some of the most common meals for rural Ethiopians, almost always consumed with *injera* bread, made from the cereal tef. This combination of grasspea and cereal food sources also provides the broad amino acid profile to reduce the risk of ODAP toxicity, which is further assisted via the general diversification of diets in Ethiopia over the past decades.

Research in Ethiopia finds that understanding around grasspea toxicity and safe consumption is broad and varied. Ethiopia has historically experienced outbreaks of neurolethyrism, particularly during severe famines of the 1970s and 1980s when grasspea became one of the few remaining food sources. Subsequently, grasspea is widely known in Ethiopia to carry some risk, leading to a stigma around the crop and association of grasspea consumers as impoverished - forced to eat a risky crop due to a lack of agency. This view is however changing, and many believe that grasspea consumption today is safe, partly due to local processing methods of soaking and extended cooking (Akalu, et al., 1998; Heaton et al. 2025). These same views, combined with rising consumption levels of the crop, are also

breaking the stigma across local growing areas of grasspea being a poor person's crop. The change in local perception of grasspea safety is supported by the apparent lack of neurolethyrism outbreaks⁵ and the increasing number of individuals who report safely consuming the crop. This has also led to a rising belief that Ethiopian grasspea varieties today contain less toxins than in the past, although there is no evidence to show such a change. Local methods of food processing to reduce toxicity are certainly contributing towards safe consumption of grasspea, but our previous work finds that these methods are varied, and not all supported by evidence of how ODAP toxicity manifests. For instance, some believe the toxicity is caused by walking through grasspea fields, picking the crop on a cloudy day, drinking milk with grasspea meals or sleeping on grasspea straw - ideas which run counter to understanding what causes ODAP toxicity. At the same time, there have been no shock weather events to rival those in the 70s and 80s that created the situation where many Ethiopians were forced to survive predominantly on grasspea harvests. It therefore seems that many may be consuming the crop in the belief that this is safe to consume, while unknowingly being protected against toxicity by balanced diets.

The concern therefore is a potential perfect storm forming for future Ethiopian neurolethyrism outbreaks. Grasspea production, demand and consumption is rising. At the same time, climate change is globally causing seasonal shifts and the

4. It is common practice across Ethiopia for Christians to avoid animal products for two set fasting days a week and over specific religious events.

5. Although the actual neurolethyrism figures are unclear as little census data exists and individuals who contract the disease are stigmatised and marginalised. Despite an absence of reported outbreaks, we find that villagers in grasspea growing areas regularly know of others with neurolethyrism symptoms (Heaton et al. 2025).

increased prevalence of shock weather events. Across the rain-fed majority of smallholder agriculture in Ethiopia, this therefore raises the chance of future shock events that cause harvest failures of crops less resilient than grasspea. Where these happen, dietary diversity will decrease and consumption of grasspea will likely remain across many part of Ethiopia. These shock events will also restrict the resources required for processing methods for ODAP removal, reducing their efficacy. Under the belief that modern grasspea lines are safer, consumers will continue to rely on the crop as a more dominant part of their diet for extended periods of time. Instability and other factors that restrict the supply chains which provide dietary diversity further increase the vulnerability of local communities. Such instability has also become commonplace across many part of Ethiopia and shows little sign of abating. Overall, this scenario of increased grasspea consumption without the appropriate toxicity risk mitigation measures raises the potential for neurotoxicity outbreaks and is a route that can and must be avoided.

There are numerous paths to avoid the aforementioned scenario. Perhaps the most obvious, and one that historically has been tried before in other countries, is the banning of grasspea to prevent consumption. This approach however both

overlooks the value grasspea is already offering to many Ethiopian smallholders and the slim likelihood of enforcing such a ruling. Examples can be taken from the grasspea bans in India, prohibiting grasspea production or blocking it from human consumption and yet grasspea cultivation has continued throughout. Ethiopian local administrations also brought in restrictions or warnings against grasspea cultivation following the neurotoxicity outbreaks and still the crop has persisted due to the useful qualities it provides. These examples demonstrate the futility of attempting to ban the cultivation and consumption of a crop that people turn to when other crops fail. An alternative, and more pragmatic approach would be to appreciate the value grasspea offers and instead work to proliferate safer and more productive grasspea varieties across Ethiopia. These would be grasspea varieties with low or no ODAP content, combined with improved agronomic traits. Bringing these varieties to the field would enable farmers to gain even more from an already dependable crop, but without the caveat of risk under specific circumstances. Based on our previous research, we believe this latter approach of delivering improved grasspea is the best way to support Ethiopian farmers while also protecting them against potential toxicity.

Ethiopian grasspea systems, varieties and potential

Since our aim is to make use of the potential of grasspea for resilience while safeguarding consumers against neurotoxicity, it is useful to understand the context of how Ethiopian farmers acquire grasspea seed.

Ethiopian farmers access grasspea seed entirely through saved seed and informal seed systems of local markets and travelling sellers. This is contrary to formal seed systems of seed production through private or government-owned seed companies and sale through official wholesalers, agro-dealers and other formalised businesses. This situation is however not unique to grasspea. Firstly, a general pattern across much of the world is that formal seed systems focus on major and cash crops. These crops offer the sufficient financial returns to justify higher selling prices and repeat purchase, that covers the cost of investment. Legumes seldom offer these same returns, and so are generally poorly represented or absent in seed produced through the formal system, which focuses on cereals for staple foods (maize, wheat, etc.). Secondly, even where these legumes are present, the vast majority of smallholders source most seed from informal systems (McGuire and Sperling 2016). This is not

to say that grasspea seed should remain absent on formal seed markets, but to note that its inclusion should not lead to the assumption that farmers will then uptake these varieties. Presently then, grasspea cultivation is common and expanding, and this is entirely the result of informal seed exchange.

Ethiopian government seed purchase

An important seed system feature to consider for Ethiopia particularly is that 'direct seed marketing' from private actors to farmers is a relatively recent change. Chronic food insecurity through the country during the 70s and 80s led to the government's large-scale purchase and distribution of staple crops such as tef, wheat and pulses (Beko 2017). The Ethiopian government formalised this approach by establishing state-affiliated organisations such as the Ethiopian Seed Enterprise (ESE), Agricultural Inputs Supply Enterprise (AISE) and regional public seed enterprises. These groups were created to ensure that smallholders had consistent access to improved seed to support local productivity. The process worked through the Ethiopian government commissioning large-scale multiplication through farmers, private and state-owned seed companies.

This seed was then collected, inspected and distributed by regional and *woreda* (district) bureaus of agriculture (RBoAs/WBoAs) and farmer cooperatives. The products are sometimes provided at subsidised price.

Despite the initial benefits of ensuring a large number of smallholders could access seed, several challenges have emerged from this approach. The system provided farmers with limited choices, often faced timeliness issues in seed reaching farmers, led to inefficiencies in demanding forecasting and seed distribution, resulted in seed wastage, encouraged a dependence on subsidies and stifled private sector innovation. Consequently, the recent decade has seen Ethiopia attempt to move to more of a market-orientated seed system approach, including trials with the 'direct seed marketing' (DSM) modality since first being piloted in 2011 (Mekonnen, 2021). The move is hoped to improve efficiencies and responsiveness of the seed industry to localised farmer needs, also aiming to improve varietal diversity and quality of seed reaching farmers. This approach also seeks to reduce government seed spending and promote a more sustainable option through markets. As such, the Ethiopian government has been creating policy and incentives to encourage the growth of seed enterprises and the engagement of farmers with purchasing formal certified seed.

The DSM approach has been used to distribute primarily seed for cereal crops, and with mixed results. Initial reports suggest the DSM approach has led to a 15 percentage point increase in the proportion of farmers purchasing maize and an 18% increase in maize yields (Mekonnen et al. 2025). Wheat and tef purchases however appear unaffected by the change, partly due to their reproductive ease of resowing⁶ presenting challenges to commercial sustainability (Kumar & Sonkar 2021). The approach therefore appears to be offering crop-specific outcomes rather than general improvements and sustainability across seed systems, suggesting the need for tailored approaches across species. This final point is relevant for grasspea production, which is readily reproduced by farmers saving seed due to the open-pollinated nature of the crop.

We will revisit these systems in their potential for the deployment of improved grasspea but first we will

Improved grasspea lines and considerations for expansion

Essentially all grasspea grown by Ethiopian farmers is a mixture of landraces descended from generations of farmers' exchange of seed (Girma and Korbu 2012). The grasspea diversity across Ethiopia is therefore likely highland locally adapted to the agro-ecologies (Shiferaw et al. 2012; Tadesse and Bekele 2002). No grasspea seed is produced for sale by the formal seed system, and there appears to be no record of this ever having been the case. This is not surprising given the national focus on other legumes, such as chickpea and lentil. Another reason for the lack of grasspea on formal seed systems is that, despite over 50 years of research on grasspea in Ethiopia, only a single line, named Wasie, was officially released in 2006 with the assistance of EIAR. Wasie was originally identified by ICARDA as having <0.1% ODAP concentration, offered a high yield (1.67 ton ha⁻¹) and was resistant to powdery mildew (Kumar et al. 2011). On these grounds, the line was officially listed as a variety in Ethiopia, and remains the only improved grasspea variety in the country to this day.

Despite the potential improved safety potential of Wasie, key informant interviews from NISD research indicate that production and adoption has been almost non-existent. As mentioned, some of this likely stems from producers wanting to focus on more conventionally profitable crops. Others might also be concerned about the older stigma associated with grasspea, particularly where seed producers might be based in urban areas away from the changes taking place in grasspea growing rural areas. The production of grasspea might also be seen as a risky gamble by businesses to recoup production costs and make a profit on seed sales due to the low price of grasspea grain and the prevalence of farmer to farmer sharing of grasspea seed. Production of formal seed brings multiple costs in growing, testing, processing, packaging and delivering seed which must be considered in the final sales price. These costs would make final sales prices comparatively high compared to local grasspea options. The open-pollinated nature of grasspea also poses a

6. Wheat is self pollinating and tef is open pollinated, making them both viable for farmers to repeatedly save seed and regrow.

challenge to the sustainability model of supplying improved grasspea where smallholders are likely to regrow saved seed, rather than repurchase seed from producers.

A more general concern exists around the delivery of a low-ODAP line which farmers may choose to save locally and repeatedly resow. Doing so is possible due to the open-pollinated nature of grasspea, but this risks affecting the safety of the variety. Grasspea has around a 5-20% outcrossing rate, influenced by cross-pollination by insects, affecting the underlying genetics which could influence traits like ODAP content (Girma and Korbu 2012). The result could be farmers resowing varieties which they believe to be low ODAP which might actually show variation in this trait. This effect would be greater in areas of mixed ODAP trait grasspea, and lower in areas of high homogeneity for low-ODAP plants. Irrespective, this outcrossing consequence could lead to consumers underestimating the toxicity of the crop. This demonstrates the importance of considering how users will handle low-ODAP varieties after adoption, and how to raise local awareness around toxicity concerns. It also demonstrates an additional reason to encourage widespread, rapid uptake of low-ODAP grasspea to reduce the outcrossing

influence on toxicity for those that repeatedly resow. These concerns should however be compared with the increasing use of low-ODAP grasspea across Bangladesh and India, where farmers will be resowing varieties and yet incidence of neurotoxicity remains low, likely as a result of toxicity processing and eating grasspea as part of a balanced diet (Kumar et al., 2021; Lambein et al., 2019).

Toxicity is however only one trait and farmers choose grasspea for a range of qualities. Our previous research confirms that farmers are marginally interested in low or no-ODAP varieties, but far more interested in varieties with improved resilience to weather, pest and disease pressures (Heaton et al. 2025). These findings serve as a reminder that while there is a public health incentive to encourage adoption of safer grasspea varieties, foregrounding this trait to farmers is unlikely to encourage investment. Instead, there are likely a diverse range of locally-valued growing and consumer traits that farmers would be more inclined to invest in, such as higher yield, as indicated in some interviews. Bundling safer grasspea traits with these locally valued traits, and leading a point of sale with these qualities is therefore more likely to encourage investment rather than reliance on safety traits alone.

Legume comparisons in Ethiopia

One potential way to consider the future for grasspea expansion in Ethiopia is to compare the situation for other legume crops. While each of these crops offers a slightly different niche, there are similar patterns in terms of markets and uses across legumes.

Chickpea, lentils and faba bean are grown on around 221, 220 and 505 thousand hectares respectively

across Ethiopia, with grasspea grown on around 153 thousand hectares (Alemayehu et al. 2024; Heaton et al. 2025). Chickpeas and lentils are the primary ingredients in commonly eaten Ethiopian stews *shiro* and *misir wot*, and faba beans make up a breakfast dish called *ful*. Chickpeas are also an important export crop. These three alternatives differ slightly in their seed production and value chain set up.

Feature	Chickpea	Lentil	Faba Bean	Grasspea
Seed System	Formal	Formal and informal	Formal and informal	Informal
Commercialisation	High (domestic & export)	Medium (domestic & export)	Medium (domestic)	Low, mostly subsistence
Value Chain Structure	Structured, organised	Moderately structured	Loosely structured	Informal, unstructured
Private Sector Role	Significant, active	Moderate, increasing	Limited, but emerging	Minimal to none
Improved Varieties	Widely adopted	Increasing adoption	Increasing adoption	Almost no adoption
Market Focus	Domestic & Export	Domestic & Emerging Export	Mainly domestic	Mostly household/ local use

Chickpea is widely grown across the Oromia and Amhara regions, with a strong commercialisation focus and prevalence of export markets. There is focus on the creation of improved seed creation by EIAR and ICARDA, the varieties of which are then produced through the Ethiopian Seed Enterprise, regional seed enterprises and farmer cooperatives. Clear market channels then link these farmers, cooperatives and traders with processors, exporters and international buyers; such as the Agricultural Commodity Suppliers Ethiopia. Exported chickpea mostly goes to markets across India, Pakistan and the Middle East. The picture is largely similar for lentils, with increasing attention on improved varieties, increasing commonality of value addition

Grasspea Ethiopian business case report: Introduction through sorting and packaging and a growing interest in international export markets. Despite faba bean cultivation areas and harvests being larger than both chickpea and lentils, production is almost entirely for domestic markets, with mostly informal, locally based traders and processors acquiring and preparing faba bean harvests for consolidation and wholesale from urban centres. Generally these three legumes can be seen as a gradient of established, emerging and limited involvement of improved seed and formalised actors compared to informal and localised operations. Consequently, these systems provide examples of steps and actors for comparative planning of how grasspea markets could be scaled up.

Only one grasspea variety has been released in Ethiopia

Cereal and legume varieties released in Ethiopia up to 2021, by crop.

Figure 3: Number of varieties released in Ethiopia since 2021. Grasspea has only one variety released, Wasie, compared to numerous releases for other crops (Plant Variety Release, Protection and Seed Quality Control Directorate, Ethiopian Agricultural Authority, 2021).

Opportunities and threats for grasspea scale-up

In summary, there are several opportunities for the increased use of grasspea varieties, as well as some threats to this change. Grasspea’s tolerance to drought and marginal soils provides an opportunity as a climate-smart crop for a broad range of farmers. This makes grasspea cultivation particularly relevant in line with the growing emphasis on pulses as part of climate-resilient agricultural policy and action in Ethiopia. Improved grasspea varieties can offer a high-quality protein source, and particularly across resource-poor areas. This nutritional quality can also be considered for livestock, where high-nutrient grasspea residues provide an additional market beyond grain, supporting both animal production and local livelihoods. As we will explore in the next sections, both the history and emerging future of Ethiopian seed systems offer opportunities for how to encourage expansion of improved grasspea varieties. Doing so offers the chance to realise

the potential for improved grasspea for Ethiopian national consumption, and invite the potential for grasspea export markets in the future, such as those that exist for chickpea and lentil.

These opportunities for grasspea proliferation must be caveated with the threats that could prevent adoption. Foremost could be the perceived risk and scepticism farmers and consumers might have for the safety of low-ODAP lines, which could limit adoption and markets. For instance, one might expect farmers to prefer other legumes (such as chickpea or lentil) which have more established markets and lack the historic stigma associated with grasspea. While this concern is valid, Ethiopian agricultural reports show that grasspea acreage and production is increasing across Ethiopia, particularly so across grasspea growing areas as more turn to the crop. Recent grasspea acreage is around 70% of

chickpea and lentil crops, and shows a consistent rise in production over the last 20 years (Ethiopian Statistical Service, 2025). It therefore seems that many Ethiopians today are not bound by historic concerns about the safety of the crop and instead are shifting to scale up production. Nonetheless, medical researchers and public health professionals should be engaged in the design and implementation of interventions promoting grasspea production to properly assess the risk of neurotoxicity and to develop mitigation measures.

The scale up of grasspea production provides a potential market opportunity for improved, safer grasspea. After all, if farmers are shifting to grasspea, it seems plausible that they would like varieties that give higher yields and other beneficial traits as well as being safer to consume. The challenge is the assumption that farmers will be willing to pay for these new varieties, especially when local grasspea seed might be more cheaply accessed and local grasspea grain prices remain low, especially where there might be limited markets, reducing the potential for the return on investment from improved grasspea purchase. Interviews with small, local seed producers show that they would be willing to produce grasspea seed as long as there was proven farmer demand for the crop. However, low marketability or opportunities for commercialisation of grasspea products could therefore limit local demand for improved seed, and therefore needs to be considered as part of the intervention process to scale up the crop. This same demand shortfall, or even the perception of it, could also disincentivise formal seed actors from producing grasspea seed out of

concern for recuperating costs and ongoing business sustainability. This is particularly so given that farmers are able to resow grasspea seed, reducing the need to return to sellers to restock. Systems for improved grasspea deployment therefore need to consider ways to make more long-term models for improved grasspea supply, without assuming that the system will be viable on an approach that might work for higher value crops.

Another challenge lies in the situation that improved grasspea uptake becomes too popular. Ethiopia currently has limited capacity for formal seed production and delivery to farmers. This brings a risk that either formal supply cannot keep up with demand, or that lower quality improved grasspea seed enters the system. Where farmers are unable to access ongoing improved seed, they are more likely to continue to resow seed, which brings with it the likelihood of greater diversity across targeted traits and brings a risk where this could affect ODAP levels; especially around drought periods where ODAP levels in the plant rise. Improved grasspea uptake strategies therefore need to consider how to encourage awareness around grasspea resowing, and strive to deliver ongoing availability of seed to grasspea growing areas.

There are therefore several reasons why improved grasspea varieties present opportunities for Ethiopian farmers, but also why there are threats to realising this vision. Based on these considerations, the next section shares three models for the deployment and scale-up of improved grasspea production in Ethiopia as a safe, nutritious and climate-smart crop.

Opportunities	Threats
Climate resilience and drought adaptation	Continued ODAP-related health risks
Improved food/nutritional security	Weak seed multiplication and certification
Integration into private sector seed system	Limited farmer awareness and market demand
Livestock feed market potential	Competition from more commercial pulses
Policy and institutional backing	Genetic erosion and loss of local landraces
Export and niche market potential	Environmental variability influencing ODAP levels

Grasspea deployment scenarios

In the following section, we present three potential models to bring about the widespread deployment and sustained adoption of improved grasspea varieties. These approaches include:

1. Government seed purchase and distribution of improved grasspea varieties to farmers.
2. Integrated seed sector production and marketing of improved grasspea through local seed businesses (LSBs).
3. A phased approach, drawing on the strengths of both systems to bring about improved grasspea introduction and long-term supply.

For each option we provide a summary on the approach, a stakeholder mapped theory of change, the strengths and weaknesses of each approach and the steps for implementation.

An actor level comparison for each scenario is supplied at the end of this document. This includes the role, enabling and constraining factors for each of the central actors within each scenario.

Deployment scenarios

1 GOVERNMENT SEED PURCHASE AND DISTRIBUTION.

Following the conventional government approach for rapidly sharing seed across rural areas.

2 INTEGRATED SEED SECTOR

Drawing on an emerging community-empowering approach to achieve quality seed provision through local entrepreneurship.

3 PHASED APPROACH

A combined approach bringing together the strengths of scenarios one and two.

Scenario 1: Government seed buying

As mentioned earlier, Ethiopia has long had a system of government purchase and distribution of seed. This system was essential in providing seed availability and access through low-cost planting materials to farmers across the country, ensuring that marginalised groups or farmers in weather shock areas were able to continue farming. The system provided a state-led approach to maintain resilience despite climate pressures.

More recently, however, Ethiopian seed strategy seeks to shift from a state-led to a market-oriented system in an approach known as 'direct seed marketing' (DSM). This approach is seen as a more efficient and decentralised method to support seed sector growth. DSM has been most successful with maize, and, to a lesser extent, wheat and tef, but less so for legumes and indigenous crops. While the government strategy is to shift to greater private-sector involvement in seed production and distribution, the extent to phase out government purchase entirely depends on the

potential for robust markets and the capacity of private sector actors to meet farmer demands for all crops. Crops where this shift will struggle most will likely be those which can be self-pollinated, rely heavily on informal seed systems and those with limited markets. For crops fitting into these categories the risk is likely too high for private actors to gamble production costs in the hope of financial sustainability through farmer repurchase. For these kinds of crops, it seems that a private-sector led method is unlikely to provide a sustainable method for ongoing adoption of improved varieties.

Grasspea falls into the category of crops that could struggle with such a deployment approach. The long-established method of government production and distribution of seed however provides a mechanism by which improved grasspea seed could be scaled up and shared across regions. In this first scenario, we explore the approach of how this state-led system could be harnessed to deploy improved grasspea.

Approach

Our vision for how this system operates for improved grasspea takes place over two stages: an initial demand creation stage which creates the scenario for the ongoing government seed purchase cycle. This is detailed in the theory of change (Figure 4).

The initial demand creation stage is required as

farmers might not be aware of new varieties of grasspea and the benefits they offer. This step also recognises that EIAR, its affiliate national research centres and Regional Agricultural Research Institutes (RARI) may have other grasspea varieties in development in addition to Wasie. This first stage begins with the Ethiopian government, specifically the

Figure 4: The scenario one theory of change for government purchase and distribution of improved grasspea seed. Acronyms: EIAR- Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research; MoA - Ministry of Agriculture; WBoA - Woreda Bureau; EAA - Ethiopian Agricultural Authority.

Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) and Regional Bureaus of Agriculture (RBoAs) mobilising both researchers and seed enterprises to exchange grasspea varieties, bulk these up and share them with *woreda* bureaus of agriculture (WBoAs) to share with model farmers. The aim is for these first model farmers to trial the improved varieties for local farming and consumption needs, share this experience with other farmers and provide a conduit to learn local interest and needs from improved grasspea. These activities then move into the start of the government seed purchase cycle.

Development Agents (DAs), or extension workers, assigned by the WBoA then engage with farmers to collect information on (1) local needs from improved grasspea and (2) local demand forecasting for future seed. DAs feed the needs assessment findings back to research groups, which constitute both regional, national and international grasspea researchers. The international research community is involved to draw on wider research, and support trait improvement by EIAR nationally. This connection with local farmer needs to international research also serves as a direct link for the grasspea community to understand user needs in Ethiopia for future research. Any improved grasspea varieties are then developed by EIAR, registered and shared with seed companies for future multiplication.

The demand forecasting from DAs feeds back to MoA and seed enterprises tasked with the multiplication of improved grasspea seed. The demand forecasting helps the government to estimate the orders from

the state-owned seed enterprises (who are likely to produce the seed at lower cost than private seed companies), as well as confirming the demand for improved grasspea varieties as part of the programme. Based on these forecasts, budget and local agricultural strategy, the government then requests multiplication of improved grasspea from seed enterprises.

State-owned seed enterprises multiply improved grasspea seed based on the best varieties for the context, which they identify through engagement with Ethiopian research. Regulators then confirm the quality of this seed, giving the confidence to purchase the seed order. ESE and RSEs then share this seed with the RBoAs to distribute to farmers through WBoAs across the target area. MoA would decide how much to subsidise the price of improved grasspea seed, with the maximum being free provision. Farmers then acquire this seed and grow it for improved harvests of safer grasspea.

The overall cycle of activities would then repeat, seeking to encourage wider growth of improved grasspea, replacing previous landraces with safer varieties. The approach would be implemented at a *woreda* level, chosen as those in high grasspea producing areas but also those most at risk of climate shocks. The approach would then scale-up through the addition of further *woredas*, starting with the initial demand creation stage, which could be supplied with seeds and farmer representatives from established improved grasspea growing areas.

Rationale, strengths and weaknesses

There are several strengths to the government purchase and distribution approach. The immediate benefit of the government purchase approach is that it makes formal seed sector multiplication of grasspea possible. The assured, repeat purchase of seed by MoA would make grasspea a more economically viable choice for state-owned seed businesses to multiply grasspea seed. This approach avoids the risk that farmers would be unwilling to pay the cost for improved grasspea seed required to recuperate private sector multiplication. Further, the government subsidy helps better ensure that farmers can afford the improved grasspea seed. This is particularly important given that farmers at most risk of neurolethyrism are also likely to be impoverished and the higher prices for formally produced improved seed might be prohibitive.

A clear strength of the government purchase approach is the potential for rapid and large-scale distribution

of improved grasspea seed. This approach is also the simplest of our three options, working within an existing and long-standing Ethiopian system for seed provision. The MoA works with a network of research institutes, BoAs and seed enterprises across the country. These networks are well integrated with farmer networks, providing detailed understanding of conditions, direct links to users and the potential for information to feedback through these networks. These systems not only provide a mechanism by which to get seed to farmers, but also an accessible interface that farmers are familiar with. This familiarity could be important given that farmers cannot visually distinguish low ODAP varieties, and so must believe the supplier.

Another strength of building on this system is that it combines provision of the improved grasspea seed with ongoing agricultural extension and monitoring of the system. Doing so provides a chance for ongoing

monitoring of how improved grasspea can be used and the effect it has on local climate resilience efforts.

The government purchase approach does however entail several weaknesses that pose threats to the operations and sustainability of using this system for improved grasspea proliferation. The first is the potential reluctance of the MoA to prioritise and dedicate resources to grasspea given the crop's relatively limited consumption and low commercial viability. Priority crops for the Ethiopian government are staple foods like wheat, maize, and tef, and those with high value on domestic and international markets, such as coffee, livestock, chickpea, and sesame. A second weakness is that the use of this system might appear to be outdated, and contrary to the general strategy the Ethiopian government is encouraging to shift to private-sector led seed marketing. Many of the arguments of the potential for inefficiencies related to the government provision of seed might also apply to this model for grasspea. While direct seed selling from private seed sellers seems unlikely to be attractive for both companies

Grasspea Ethiopian business case report: Scenario one and farmers, the MoA may be reluctant to change tack and add another crop to the older state-led provision approach. Doing so would also add another cost to government spending, which the DSM model offered an alternative to. The MoA might be happy to accept this cost on nutrition, public health and improved rural resilience grounds where improved grasspea provides not just another crop but also a way to combat neurolethyrism incidence and protect rural communities.

Even in the situation where the government accepts these costs, the sustainability of the system remains dependent on ongoing public investment, raising questions about the long-term provision of improved grasspea. On one hand, this could mean that improved grasspea seed supply ends with a change in state strategy and spending. On the other hand, this might not matter as much if grasspea sales have become more widespread by this time, and so a less risky option for companies to continue to market through private channels.

Implementation plan

1

Approval by Ethiopian Government. The first steps to implementing this scenario involve engagement with the MoA and EIAR to lobby for the use of government investment for purchase of low toxin, improved grasspea varieties. This could take place as a series of in-person meetings and should be supported by data on grasspea production and potential for food and nutrition security and livelihood improvement. We suggest this approach starts by choosing two pilot locations in grasspea growing areas to serve as case studies for reception by farmers and the performance of the improved varieties in farmers' fields. These meetings should be done in collaboration with EIAR to showcase the available improved varieties, such as Wasie, that could be deployed on government channels. These meetings should seek to show how the provision of improved grasspea provides an effective way to build rural climate resilience, while avoiding the potential public health disaster of neurolethyrism outbreaks during shock weather events.

2

Initial seed multiplication and demonstration. Once the MoA confirms support to commission grasspea sales, the next step involves multiplying available improved grasspea for use as part of the initial demand creation phase. *Woreda* agricultural extension staff (DAs) need to work with seed enterprises to create demonstration areas and to identify farmers as the initial farmers to grow improved seed. Finalised procurement plans need to go through the normal MoA system for seed enterprises to acquire. For example, either to existing contracts or a tender agreement. Regulators should perform a mid-season ODAP level confirmation check performed as part of the regulatory check as part of the certification process before release.

ESP should facilitate activities around the demonstration event to ensure that communications and farmer engagement activities take place to share the news about the improved grasspea varieties and the beneficial traits they offer. During this activity, farmers should be encouraged to visit the plots, see the harvests and try the resulting products. Representatives from the MoA, RBoAs, research institutes,

and current and potential grasspea buyers and processors should also be invited to attend these events to see demand and learn about the safer varieties. The aim is to spread the word about the benefits of improved grasspea and direct farmers to the channels through which they can access these varieties as well as markets for their product. DAs should also feed this information back to research centres and seed companies to confirm needed traits and seed performance at the field.

3

Supply initial farmers with seed and share findings. The chosen seed company will supply some of the farmers who attended the demonstration event with free seed. The aim is to stimulate local model farmers to try the improved grasspea lines in their own fields. DAs should engage with these farmers to document how the improved lines perform in local contexts and how consumers find the traits. The findings from these engagements should feed back to seed companies

4

Demand forecasting and commission. ESP and EOSA should engage with WBoAs to estimate grasspea seed demand for the year ahead. Based on farmer engagement, this must include clear targets for certified seed volume for each distribution area, and a plan detailing when and how the seed will reach these locations. Close working between extension workers and farmers will be critical for this forecasting. Developing these plans should require the encouragement of national Ethiopian government representatives, which should be facilitated by ESP.

The forecast, production requirements and distribution strategy should be agreed upon by the MoA and RBoA staff who will purchase the amount. This plan should be agreed upon before either being shared with the appropriate enterprise or being written for a tender, depending on the preferred working method for the local management. This agreement will include the close working between the company and DAs to distribute the seed.

5

Production and quality checking. The seed enterprise gains access to the improved grasspea germplasm and multiplies the seed. The seed is regulated in accordance with normal Ethiopian quality control processes, with the addition of an ODAP confirmation step which is carried out in collaboration with EIAR. Seed that meets all regulatory checks is prepared for delivery and the government updated with the fulfilment status of the consignment.

6

Government procurement and distribution. Once the consignment is complete, the seed is purchased by the MoA and released for distribution. Distribution takes place through WBoAs, with the inclusion of farmer cooperatives if needed.

Prior to delivery ESP and DAs engage in awareness promoting activities to signal the imminent delivery of improved grasspea seed and where this will be available for collection. DAs should identify farmer representatives in each group to act as a focal point for the collection and allocation of grasspea seed. During these engagements, DAs will continue to promote the importance of improved grasspea seed. These lead farmers will also be advised on the importance of re-buying new grasspea seed, rather than resowing seed from the previous harvest, on safety grounds.

7

Local improved grasspea production. Farmers trial and adopt improved grasspea varieties. DAs routinely connect with grasspea growers to enquire into farmer experience with the crop.

Farmer experiences and suggestions for grasspea improvement are fed back to research staff to guide ongoing grasspea breeding. This knowledge exchange either takes place through the assistance of DAs, or through the direct interaction of research staff with farmers.

8

Ongoing monitoring and forecasting. The described cycle continues to provide formally produced improved grasspea seed for rural communities. Extension and research, with the assistance of ESP, continue to monitor the ongoing cultivation of improved grasspea across target locations (key performance indicators mentioned in the next section). These metrics are fed back to the MoA and RBoAs along with an annual presentation and report on the success of the project and priority areas for future improvement.

Milestones and key performance indicators

The key milestones for this project include the following:

1. The MoA agrees to the purchase and distribution of improved grasspea seed.
2. Improved seed acquired or produced by the government seed company for the pilot experiment or to start multiplication
3. Improved grasspea seed is grown by model farmers in the locality.
4. Farm engagement events are completed in the first year and demand for improved grasspea seed is estimated for the following year.
5. Improved grasspea seed is commissioned by the MoA to supply local demand.
6. Seed companies complete the multiplication of improved grasspea seed and this consignment passes the regulatory checks.
7. Improved grasspea seed is delivered to farmers in the chosen locality.
8. Farmers in the locality confirm higher production of grasspea as a result of growing improved grasspea.

Key performance indicators for the scenario include:

- The number of farmers requesting improved seed.
- The number of farmers reporting to grow improved seed.
- The amount of grasspea seed requested for seed companies to multiply.
- The amount of grasspea seed purchased by the Ethiopian government.
- The amount of grasspea seed delivered to *woredas* for distribution.
- The local yield levels of grasspea.
- The number of *woredas* involved in improved grasspea production.
- Levels of neuroloathyrism incidence across the *woreda*.

Scenario 2: Integrated seed sector

A more recent seed system model to support farmer-led production of quality seed is that of the integrated seed sector. The integrated system leverages elements of both formal and informal seed systems to support diverse seed requirements across rural areas. It seeks to create pluralism and diversity in seed systems through promoting entrepreneurship and recognising the complementary roles of the formal and informal seed systems. The approach has also been used to enable progressive policies for dynamic seed sector development and promoting the evidence base for wider seed system reforms. Integrated seed systems are well suited to providing farmers with quality varieties and seed for locally important crops which might otherwise struggle on formal seed systems. For these reasons, they present a promising approach for the wide-scale uptake of improved grasspea varieties. In this scenario, we first provide a brief background on how integrated seed systems operate and their existence in Ethiopia, before outlining the approach by which improved grasspea could be deployed on these systems.

The integrated system works by training local actors as 'Local Seed Businesses' (LSBs) in the creation of high-quality seed and planting materials, which are regulated to deliver 'Quality-Declared Seed' (QDS). The LSB groups might be local farming groups, cooperatives or community seed exchanges. These LSBs can gain crop varieties through collaborations with formal seed actors and genebanks. The LSB training teaches how to preserve varietal lines and

the preparation and storage of high-quality seed. This model allows for research and formally derived varieties to enter more informal seed production networks.

The regulation of the QDS usually takes place through the help of government regulatory bodies or through agricultural extension agents who check the plants in the field during the growing season and the resulting seed that the LSB will market. These checks confirm the absence of diseases and that the product is clean, of high purity, good physical condition and offers a high germination rate. The QDS status is applied upon approval and gives buyers the confidence they are purchasing high-quality products.

An LSB operates as a local private seed company, but its smaller, localised nature, minimal processing and packaging and lighter regulatory approaches mean that production costs remain lower than formally produced seed. This makes the LSB model ideal for crops with lower market value that larger seed companies are reluctant to take on. For instance, in Uganda the integrated seed system strategically avoided crops already served by formal actors, such as maize, in an effort to complement rather than compete with formal actors (Mastenbroek et al., 2021). Because LSBs are embedded within their communities, they are often well placed to respond to local needs. LSBs can also provide a powerful conduit for two-way information flows between farmers and more formalised sources of crop varieties.

Integrated seed systems activities have been promoted and acted upon in Ethiopia to varying degrees since it was introduced in 2009 (Borman et al. 2013; 2020; Wageningen University 2016). under Ethiopian seed law, QDS is permitted and regulated as a distinct seed class according to Seed Proclamation No. 1262/2021. QDS is defined as seed “supplied being 90 % is certified by the producer and 10 % is by regional authority. Community-Based Seed Production (CBSP) hubs have been promoted across Ethiopia by the government, along with support from organisations such as FAO, USAID and the Agricultural Transformation Agency (now Agricultural Transformation Institute). More specifically, the Integrated Seed Sector Development (ISSD) project, coordinated by Wageningen University,

Grasspea Ethiopian business case report: Scenario two has been involved in training LSBs across all parts of the country. These LSBs initially focused on barley, faba bean, haricot bean, lentil, potato, maize, malt barley, tef and wheat, but now include 31 different cereals, legumes, oilseeds, roots and tubers, fruit and vegetables, and spices. These projects have been a success, reaching over four million households and increasing use of improved varieties by 28% (Borman et al. 2020). Consequently, integrated seed systems have been established across the country around regional hubs, and are seen as part of the future seed sector development in Ethiopian policy making (Beko 2017). As such, the integrated seed system is already in place across many parts of Ethiopia, ready as a pathway for the introduction of improved grasspea.

Approach

Bringing improved grasspea into the integrated seed system requires an initial step by the ESP to engage with the MoA and RBoAs. This engagement is to make the government aware of the potential of improved grasspea and how it can be deployed at scale through integrated seed systems. The intention of this is that the MoA agrees to mobilise the EIAR grasspea research community to register promising grasspea lines as varieties and multiply them for LSB groups. EOSA and ESP will then work to connect these research groups with existing or potential LSBs (such as farmer cooperative or community seed groups). Once the LSBs have been identified, EOSA and ESP will train the teams in the production of QDS for improved grasspea. The level of training required for this step depends on whether the farmer group is already an established LSB or a new group to the practice. Part of this training will focus on the toxicity of the grasspea seed and the importance of practices to maintain these low-toxicity traits - including refreshing seed from research sources.

The next stages onwards begin the QDS seed cycle that continues to be managed by the LSB, with supporting collaboration from R/WBoAs and RARIs. The first step is that the LSB produces improved grasspea seed from the initial seed provision from EIAR or RARIs. This practice is checked for quality by government regulators or DAs to confirm the absence of disease in the field and the resulting seed product.

The LSB raises local awareness of these new grasspea varieties and the benefits they offer through inviting farmers to participatory events. DAs are also made aware of these events and encourage farmers in grasspea growing areas to attend. Participatory events take place both during the growing season

and after the seed is harvested so that farmers can see the performance of the crop in the field and taste it as a processed food product. MoA, RBoA, EIAR and RARI representatives and DAs are invited to these events so that they can also see local interest in improved grasspea. This helps build advocacy with the government for expansion of improved grasspea deployment through integrated seed systems. It also helps DAs identify local interest and further potential for improved grasspea. Current and potential grasspea buyers and processors attend these events to see demand, learn about the safer varieties and what they can offer to consumers. These representatives are introduced to the group, so that farmers can identify potential markets for where to sell improved grasspea, and buyers can identify farmers with safer grasspea varieties that they can trust. The overall aim of this connection is to stimulate local markets for improved grasspea. Research and crop breeding groups attend these events as a way to encourage two-way information exchange on grasspea needs and potential. Researchers at these events share the advances they are making with grasspea and farmers, who are represented through the LSB, share both agricultural and consumer traits that they would like to see improved in future grasspea varieties. Overall these LSB-led events are demand forums, where farmers can obtain improved grasspea seed while also gaining market intelligence and guiding future grasspea improvement.

Through farmers growing local seed and interacting with new grasspea markets, demand increases for improved grasspea from LSB sources, providing the sustainability of the model through ongoing purchase of grasspea QDS products as part of local entrepreneurship. The ongoing experiences by

farmers continue to feed into the demand forums that guide future grasspea improvement and expansion. These activities continue to feedback to research to demonstrate impact and needs for grasspea research. All of this feeds back to the government to continue to mobilise DAs and regulators to support the ongoing delivery of QDS products. The system operates semi-autonomously from LSB leadership and expands to meet local needs, without need of direct government funding.

The model would be deployed to pilot grasspea growing areas where LSBs already exist, or where new LSBs are being established. Locally, the system scales organically in response to local demand and the availability of improved grasspea seed. The approach can be scaled more widely through expansion across grasspea growing *woredas* with the exchange of improved grasspea seed and training of new LSBs by currently operating LSBs.

Rationale, strengths and weaknesses

A clear benefit of the integrated seed sector approach is that it brings formal seed sector products and links them with the strengths of informal systems. This is particularly important for grasspea, which has traditionally had more limited market potential than other major crops or more established legumes, making independent seed producers less likely to invest the upfront costs in seed production. While our first scenario avoids this challenge by removing the business risk for companies producing grasspea, the integrated approach addresses this risk by supporting smaller, locally based businesses to lead production, who face lower overheads to seed production and sale. The result is that LSBs can sell improved grasspea at lower prices than other private sector counterparts, and remain economically viable for the ongoing sustainability of the business. The focus will also be on LSBs operating in geographies with high grasspea production, allowing them to leverage existing demand. This approach continues to work successfully for other less market-focused crops in Ethiopia, raising the likelihood of this approach being economically viable for grasspea on LSBs. From the farmer side, lower prices ensure that seed remains accessible, which again is essential given the prevalence of grasspea cultivation with marginalised farmers.

Having farmers lead on improved grasspea production also brings benefits for local acceptance and adaptation. Smallholders can be risk averse to new farming technologies, and this might be particularly around changes to practices they rely on as a safety net when other approaches fail. Having farmers test, confirm and promote improved grasspea might therefore provide a more known and trusted voice for farmers to rely upon. LSB farmers might also be more aware of connections across rural areas, improving seed availability in being able to reach marginalised groups who might otherwise not be in contact with formalised channels for seed. Again, this is particularly important given the association of grasspea with marginalised groups,

who might be most at risk of neurolethyrism. The ability of LSB members to connect to these groups also provides another strength to this approach as conduits for two-way knowledge exchange. As much as LSBs can bring information to these groups, their position as community members can further enable information sharing from local actors of preferences and needs. This ongoing interaction means that LSBs can become a knowledge bank for traits that farmers and consumers need, helping to inform breeds and connect users with new varieties for their needs. This system is not constrained to information, but can also be used to source landraces that offer locally valued traits, to be safe-guarded in genebanks and incorporated into breeding efforts - something that could be particularly helpful for grasspea given the widespread and long history of landraces across Ethiopia. This same two-way exchange is difficult to achieve in more formalised systems, where interactions are more transactional and rarely have the chance to give feedback to breeders.

This last paragraph touches on the potential benefits LSBs can have for local empowerment. At their simplest, integrated systems offer a capacity support system to support local livelihoods. Both these changes, and improvement in qualities to seed production and storage can also serve to support local resilience efforts. These same systems however also offer the opportunity to support bottom-up efforts to champion farmers' voices and empower farming communities to push for the changes they require. Rather than attempt to replace farmer seed systems with formalised options, integrated systems support the continued existence of these networks and communities which, again, can be beneficial for local seed security in remote areas during shocks when supply chains may stop.

This integrated approach therefore not only offers a potentially powerful approach to bring improved grasspea to the field, but also to place this right at the heart of communities which grow grasspea,

increasing accessibility and availability of seed while also providing another income stream for local livelihoods and empowering local communities.

There are however some challenges with the integrated approach for improved grasspea distribution. The first, perhaps most apparent from the theory of change (Figure 5), is that this approach requires a complex arrangement of different actors working together. It requires coordination between government, research, DAs, LSBs and local traders, any one of whom may have limited time and capacity to focus on improved grasspea. Some of this complexity might be avoided where the project engages with ongoing LSB operations, where these systems are already established. The ongoing ESP collaboration could be well-placed to navigate these actors and build close working.

Key to the operation depends on the role of EIAR research to provide improved grasspea varieties to LSBs, which might not be a priority for the research institute without MoA encouragement. This matters not only for the initial action but also the ongoing improvement of grasspea traits by Ethiopian research in response to LSB participatory activities. Where this ongoing commitment waivers, LSBs will have limited capacity to respond to ongoing farmer needs from improved grasspea and risk recycling the initially given grasspea seed.

While LSBs can be highly effective at producing seed, there is a risk that ongoing seed cycling leads to the dilution of improved traits, which also could affect the low ODAP trait. Since LSBs have no way to track this trait, this could lead to the sale of grasspea seed with variation in ODAP levels, causing a situation where consumers incorrectly believe they are growing and consuming low-toxin varieties.

Another weakness with this system is that improved grasspea uptake might be slow, and the assumption remains that farmers are interested in the improved

Grasspea Ethiopian business case report: Scenario two grasspea lines LSBs offer. The initial production of seed by LSBs might be limited, restricting the amount of improved grasspea that the operation is able to sell as QDS. Even where sufficient seed is produced, farmers may have limited interest in improved grasspea varieties, especially without effective demonstrations and extension sharing the value improved grasspea offers. Where farmers are interested in grasspea QDS, farmers might still be unwilling to pay for a crop that they might be able to obtain freely from their own sources. Alternatively, some may purchase the seed once to obtain the variety, but not repeatedly purchase new seed. Again, this cycling brings concerns over successive variation in ODAP levels. Part of the likelihood for grasspea to be continually repurchased depends on the development of grasspea markets, where higher yields provide greater harvests for sale. Where these markets are more limited, higher yields of grasspea might be a lower priority compared to markets for other legumes or more commercially viable crops. This demonstrates the importance of encouraging local markets for grasspea use around LSBs, to raise interest in improved grasspea QDS.

Finally, although integrated seed systems offer the potential for an economically sustainable way to continue to produce grasspea seed, the system requires initial funding for the training and close working of actors. The ongoing research and breeding will also require investment as part of national budgets for crop improvement. These budget considerations are important for the ongoing scale up of integrated grasspea production, particularly in areas where LSB operations do not already exist. The integrated model therefore offers a path to a self-sustaining production system, but one that will still require some external investment for the ongoing improvement and scale up of operations. These funds could however be legitimised under public health grounds and in support of climate adaptation planning.

Figure 5: The scenario two theory of change for integrated seed system production of improved grasspea seed.

Acronyms: DAs - Development Assistants | LSB - Local Seed Business | MoA - Ministry of Agriculture
QDS - Quality Declared Seed | R/WBoAs - Regional and Woreda Bureau of Agriculture

Implementation plan

1

Approval by Ethiopian Government. Due to the importance of the MoA for the initial investment and advocacy for the approach, the first step requires their agreement and commitment to development of the project. This engagement should be made to appeal to Ethiopian climate adaptation planning, the public health concerns from grasspea consumption and as part of ongoing seed system development in collaboration with ESP and partners. EIAR must be involved in these initial meetings to ensure close working from the project onset between research and the LSB approach.

2

Participatory coordination workshop. The ongoing success of the LSB depends on its close working with research institutes. The project initiation should therefore include two participatory workshops. The first would have LSB members visit the research centre to see the improved grasspea growing in the field and for research staff to share the trait improvements in the varieties as compared to landraces. The second workshop would be where researchers and extension agents visit the LSB site to understand field conditions, LSB operations and locally valued traits.

3

Capacity development. The LSB will require training depending on the establishment of the integrated seed system in the local area. Where LSBs exist, this stage will involve sharing grasspea germplasm and providing training in the production of high quality grasspea seed. EOSA will lead this training in collaboration with ESP, working with local farmers and research groups. After the completion of this training, LSBs will be able to produce QDS for improved grasspea seed. Extension agents continue to work closely with LSBs to ensure they are comfortable with the process and the reliable production of safe grasspea seed.

4

Production & quality assurance. The LSB conducts multiplication and processing of improved grasspea seed. EOSA and ESP stay in close communication with the LSB during the first cycle to ensure the careful delivery of each production step. Government regulatory agents or extension agents evaluate the grasspea plants during the mid-season and post-season to confirm lack of disease, and confirm the purity and quality of the seed. Seed that passes regulatory checks is awarded QDS status and made available for sale. LSB improved grasspea seed capacity is recorded.

5

Demonstration and demand forums. A key stage to build demand for improved grasspea will be the ability of the LSB and project collaborators to raise the product's visibility, communicate the importance of these improvements and the potential for market growth. This includes developing a plan to be led by the LSB to raise visibility of improved grasspea seed. The LSB will lead the demonstration engagements as farmer-farmer exchanges, where LSB members share the range of improved grasspea varieties and beneficial traits they offer. These demonstrations should include agronomic traits as well as consumer traits, with grasspea dishes having been prepared for attendees to try. LSB members at these events must also welcome input from farmers to learn what traits are locally sought after from grasspea landraces.

Agricultural extension workers should point farmers to these events, as well as attending themselves to show support for the LSB activities and validation of the low-ODAP trait. Extension agents should also encourage prospective buyers and processors of grasspea products to attend the event, to learn about the safer grasspea varieties and the potential they have for market. Extension agents should work with LSB management members to ensure potential buyers should also have the opportunity to engage with farmers and share their requirements.

ESP should ensure that researchers are invited to the demonstration events to gain understanding of the demand for grasspea and to identify traits for further development. This connection needs to be equal, honest and transparent, recognising the potential of LSBs as a conduit to extend and inform grasspea improvement through both research and farmer input. ESP should facilitate the start of this relationship, ensuring multiple initial and annual meetings where both stakeholder groups are able to contribute equally. This relationship should also encourage farmers to landraces with locally valued traits, for this germplasm to feed into conservation and trait improvement activities.

6

Sale and delivery of QDS. Following the confirmation of the QDS label, the LSB can begin marketing improved grasspea seed. EOSA should support these stages with new LSBs or those marketing grasspea for the first time. Some of this marketing will take place during the demonstration events but LSBs must also be actively raising awareness of their activities with the wider community. Extension agents should support LSBs by signposting the production of improved grasspea varieties amongst farmers known to grow local grasspea. Most of this seed will likely be purchased directly from LSBs, but extension agents could assist with the purchase and delivery of consignments on behalf of more distant farmers and cooperatives. Farmers who have previously purchased in advance to encourage repeat purchase.

7

Monitoring & adaptation. The LSB and extension agents, with the facilitation of EOSA and ESP, should reflect on the process of improved grasspea seed multiplication, the demonstration experience, the responses of farmers, sale of seed and the resulting adoption by farmers. This should be conducted as a workshop activity and the reflections used to guide future LSB activities and engagement with farmers. Extension agents should feed into these discussions with ongoing review from wider farmers on the performance of improved grasspea seed in the field. The aim is to maintain a sense of farmer adoption tracking and feedback loops to guide adaptive management of the LSB to meet demand.

8

Scaling & sustainability. Based on step seven and the grasspea market, the LSB should expand activities to produce sufficient seed to support the local area. These activities need to take place in alignment with local needs and the introduction into the LSB system of new varieties from research centres. LSBs should aim to develop as a sustainable model, operating efficiently to meet grasspea demand. Doing so will depend on the ongoing market intelligence from extension agents to gauge local demand for LSBs to supply.

Extension workers, government administrative bodies, EOSA and ESP can support the sustainability of the LSB model by raising its visibility and sharing the importance of improved grasspea on health grounds. Similarly, these actors should continue to remind farmers of the importance to repurchase grasspea seed from LSBs, and to encourage grasspea buyers to check the source of farmers' seed before purchase. Government should be updated with these developments and encouraged to continue to maintain grasspea improvement as a priority for research.

A potential optional expansion step is for grasspea-producing LSBs to visit other LSBs that are yet to produce grasspea, and to supply training for high quality multiplication. These exchanges would take place in areas beyond the initial LSBs farmer catchment area, and could be facilitated by EOSA as part of district and regional expansion efforts.

Milestones and key performance indicators

Milestones include:

1. New LSBs are established and trained to produce improved grasspea.
2. Existing LSBs are trained in the multiplication of improved grasspea
3. LSBs successful multiply improved grasspea seed
4. LSB grasspea seed is awarded QDS status.
5. Improved grasspea demand forums are held with farmers, DAs, researchers and market actors.
6. Farmers purchase sufficient grasspea seed to cover multiplication costs and profit the LSB.
7. Significant adoption of improved grasspea takes place locally and demand for more seed increases.
8. LSBs expand grasspea multiplication activities to meet demand. This includes training other LSBs in new locations.
9. Researchers produce new grasspea germplasm based on LSB interactions, and this seed is provided to LSBs to multiply.
10. LSBs are established in new areas and trained in the cultivation of improved grasspea.

Milestones three to ten continue to be recorded annually, with attention to growth of output and collaboration over successive years.

Key performance indicators include:

- Number of LSBs established and trained in improved grasspea seed production.
- Volume of improved grasspea seed produced by LSBs (kg or tons per season).
- Number of LSBs meeting annual seed production targets aligned with local demand.
- Percentage of seed lots passing Quality Declared Seed (QDS) certification, including ODAP safety tests where feasible.
- Number of demonstration or demand forum events held annually.
- Number of buyers/processors engaged with LSBs for improved grasspea.
- Number of farmers purchasing improved grasspea seed from LSBs.
- Percentage increase in farmer demand for improved grasspea over successive seasons.
- Farmer satisfaction score with improved grasspea seed (based on yield, taste, ease of processing etc.).
- Number of new varieties released or introduced via LSBs based on local feedback.

Scenario 3: Phased approach

A final potential approach takes both scenario one and two and combines them in a phased approach to raise the likelihood of widespread and sustained adoption of improved grasspea. This suggestion stems from the possible balance that both scenarios one and two offer to one another. A major weakness of the government purchase approach is sustainability, but also it provides a potentially fast approach to bulk and distribute seed to farmer groups. Conversely the integrated approach may require more time to set up and bulk grasspea seed, but offers a more efficient and sustainable option once running, provided the market for improved grasspea exists and persists. The two approaches therefore can complement one another.

Approach

This combined approach uses the pathway outlined in scenario one for the programme start, to combine with, and eventually transition to the activities outlined in scenario two for ongoing sustainability.

The combined pipeline begins with the initial demand creation phase of scenario one, but with a wider scope to initiate the activities in both the government seed purchase approach (scenario one) and the integrated system (scenario two). This phase would be similar to the initial phases described in both the previous scenarios, but with some minor differences. The first would be the explicit awareness for all government, research and coordinating parties of the timeline of each component. This would help research groups understand the quantity and nature of improved grasspea that needed to be provided to the different actors. It also provides LSBs a timeline within which they would be expected to complete their training and become the main source of improved QDS grasspea seed for farmers.

Offering a combined approach might also make government purchase of grasspea seed appear more attractive for policymakers, as it explicitly plans a deadline for this investment in a move towards market-driven sustainability.

Such an approach might also lessen the initial demand on LSBs to both stimulate and supply widespread uptake of improved grasspea. Instead, demand could be initiated through MoA provision of subsidised or free seed, while LSBs build their capacity to meet that demand as government provisions scale down over successive years.

Monitoring is essential for the delivery of the phased approach and relies on close working of DAs and LSB representatives, facilitated through EOSA and ESP. This monitoring takes place both within each of the two approaches, and between them. Throughout the phased approach, the government purchase and LSB teams will need to monitor improved grasspea demand, multiplication and delivery; as outlined in the respective scenarios above. Additionally, further monitoring is required to track the LSB capacity to meet local improved grasspea demand, to feed this back to reduce government seed purchase accordingly and monitor the effectiveness of the transition of farmer purchase from one system to the other. We envision this handover time being estimated in advance, but informed by a feedback loop during the process. The MoA purchase system would operate in a similar format to the process described in scenario one, with the addition of a measurement and communication phase with the LSB actors. This monitoring process would analyse the quantity of seed the LSB is able to produce versus the local demand forecast. This

information would inform the timing and extent of the reduction in government seed purchase, for LSBs to begin to supply.

As the MoA scales back purchase and distribution of improved grasspea seed, DAs would point grasspea producers to the LSB suppliers. This recommendation would raise visibility of the LSB and provide further assurance that they can provide quality products. The LSB is also provided with the details of the improved grasspea seed demand and the WBoAs and any farmer cooperatives that MoA purchased seed may have previously supplied. This process could be done

Challenges & risk assessment

A clear challenge with this approach is the complexity of the system, particularly when it combines two systems which alone rely on the close working of separate actor groups. The phased approach depends not only on the initial collaboration of these groups, but the ongoing close working and communication to perform the shift from government distribution to LSB supply. The shift between operations is also time sensitive. Shifting to the LSB too early might mean it struggles to keep up with farmer demand, risking farmers being short of seed for the season or recycling their own seed. Alternatively, shifting too slowly to LSB supply could cause LSBs to struggle to find markets for their products, threatening the sustainability of the business. This phased approach therefore would require careful, and ongoing, monitoring of both systems to inform the details for the transition. Another factor that could either hinder or assist this transition depends on the price of the improved grasspea seed.

Price poses potentially the biggest challenge in the transition between government and LSB supply systems. As mentioned earlier, the lack of a large market for grasspea currently restricts the amount that farmers are likely willing to pay for improved grasspea seed. The challenge with the phased approach therefore comes in the strategy behind the degree of government subsidy and the price required by LSBs to cover seed production costs. For instance, the government might entirely cover the costs of improved grasspea, say on nutrition grounds, but this means that during the transition to LSB supply, farmers would essentially be offered a similar product but at a price. Such a transition could be received badly by farmers, and in practice lead to farmers opting to regrow their own seed rather than purchase it.⁷ This situation would also threaten the business sustainability of LSBs supplying improved grasspea. Alternatively, if the MoA under-subsidises improved grasspea during the first phase, the result

Grasspea Ethiopian business case report: Scenario three gradually, where LSBs incrementally supply more farmer groups that initially relied upon government distribution of grasspea seed. This could, for example, operate through LSBs successively supplying additional farmer cooperatives who previously relied on government distribution. Government could also begin transitioning purchases away from seed enterprises to instead purchase from LSBs, as this material would likely be a lower price for government, would provide LSBs with initial business, and ensure that LSBs were not out competed by heavily subsidised grasspea from seed enterprises.

might be that farmers fail to adopt the seed, despite government investment, instead choosing to regrow their own saved grasspea. Still, a logical way to encourage the shift from the government seed to LSBs is to position the LSB seed at a lower price than government provisions. A potential middle ground to this approach could be a sliding approach, where the subsidy for government distributed seed reduces over successive years, until it retails for a higher price than LSB products. In the first year, with the aim to encourage widespread adoption, the seed could be distributed with a full government subsidy. The degree of subsidy would then move to a graduated pay model. For instance, this could operate as a 60% to 40% subsidy for the second and third years respectively, moving to full payment in the final year. This graduated scale would complement the scale up of grasspea seed provision by LSBs, while also avoiding the experienced contrast for farmers of going from a free to paid model. The subsidy graduation module will be set at the project initiation, but decided upon each year depending on grasspea production capacity, ongoing demand and the performance of improved grasspea sales in the previous year.

In practice, the graduated approach might mean that more widespread adoption of grasspea occurs initially, but that prices increase to mimic the encouraged wider market for grasspea products, which farmers accept until they have the offer of the more economical option of purchasing from LSBs. This system could appeal to farmer investment behaviours, but it could mean an inefficiency in MoA investment where the final stages of government distribution might remain unsold in favour of LSB seed. Previous NISD discrete choice experiments can offer some insight on price setting, where farmers appear generally willing to choose improved grasspea with useful traits for up to double the current market price (Heaton et al. 2025).

7. The ongoing risks of this being potential variation in the ODAP trait with successive generations.

Implementation plan

The phased approach follows a similar implementation plan of both scenarios one and two, adjusted to complement one another. These stages are outlined briefly below to avoid repetition as they were explained earlier in this document. Here we emphasise only the areas where there are differences with the phased approach.

1

Approval by Ethiopian government. Due to the importance of the MoA for the initial investment and advocacy for the approach, the first step requires their agreement and commitment to development of the project. This engagement should be made to appeal to Ethiopian climate adaptation planning, the public health concerns from grasspea consumption and as part of ongoing seed system development in collaboration with ESP and partners. EIAR and RARIs must be involved in these initial meetings to ensure close working from the project onset between research and the LSB approach.

2

Coordination workshop to establish a joint working group. Close collaboration is required to ensure alignment between the government purchase and LSB working groups. This includes setting a transition timeline for when LSBs will begin to take over improved grasspea provision, when MoA supplied seed will scale down and when LSBs are expected to take on full production. This transition should be made with contingency buffers to allow for shortfalls or booms in multiplication of seed, and the general establishment of the LSBs. This meeting should also set the graduated subsidy scheme, the amounts and the agreed changes over the next four years.

The coordination meeting would be facilitated by ESP and EOSA, and involve actors from R/WBoAs, DAs, EIAR research, and seed enterprise and LSB representatives to ensure shared understanding across the actors prior to the initial seed multiplication stages.

3

Provision of seed and capacity development. The initial activities require the sharing of improved grasspea germplasm with the MoA chosen seed enterprises and the LSBs. The public sector seed enterprises will obtain the improved grasspea germplasm from EIAR research in order to produce the first round of seed to be supplied to LSBs.

As with scenario two, the LSBs will require training depending on the establishment of the integrated seed system in the local area, which EOSA can facilitate with both germplasm providers and the LSB members.

4

Production & quality assurance. Government regulators and DAs will conduct quality checks for seed produced by both systems. These include the conventional seed and quality checks (purity, disease resistance, germination rates, etc.) along with additional checks of ODAP levels. This ODAP monitoring will be conducted in collaboration with EIAR researchers. The final step of this stage should be the awarding of formal seed certification or QDS.

5

Demonstration and demand forums. Seed produced by public sector enterprises and LSBs will require some forms of awareness building, demonstration and demand creation to encourage improved grasspea uptake. These details have been expanded upon in the earlier scenarios. These demonstrations could involve both seed enterprises LSBs, so that farmers are aware of both sources from the start of activities. DAs, and ESP, EOSA and LSBs should also be involved in these demonstration events with farmers.

6

Demand fulfilment and transition. Seed enterprises and LSBs will both multiply seed to meet farmer demand in successive cycles. During each cycle, a check is conducted of the local demand for improved grasspea seed and the capacity of both providers to meet that demand. Where LSBs are able to support local demand, R/WBoAs commence the transition of seed provision towards LSBs, as the MoA reduces the seed requested from enterprises.

7

Transition delivery. Annual meetings are held each year with all project leads to agree the transition targets and government seed purchase amount, and to set subsidy levels. DAs will assist with the transition process, pointing farmers to LSBs and reporting challenges or opportunities for transition.

The transition depends upon careful monitoring throughout of demand forecasting, improved grasspea production capacity and the ability and willingness of farmers to switch from free or subsidised to paid seed. For instance, farmers should be consulted on the ease of accessing seed from LSBs and solutions explored where this is found to be challenging. These distribution challenges would draw on those already established during the initial phases of MoA seed distribution.

8

Scaling & sustainability. Scaling and sustainability of this scenario is delivered through the support and proliferation of LSBs across grasspea growing areas. LSBs will work with researchers and farmers to provide farmers with new grasspea varieties to raise production and meet local needs. Researchers set breeding targets based upon this feedback and draw on LSBs as the conduit to share these varietal innovations with farmers.

R/WBoAs and ESP support the sustainability of the LSB model by raising its visibility and sharing the importance of improved grasspea on health and nutrition grounds. Similarly, these actors should continue to remind farmers of the importance to repurchase grasspea seed from LSBs, and to encourage grasspea buyers to check the source of farmers' seed before purchase.

Milestones and key performance indicators

The phased approach draws on milestones from both previous scenarios, with these additional steps:

1. Initial project meeting completed and targets set for production from both MoA purchase and LSBs.
2. Subsidy scale is decided upon for the first year.
3. Improved grasspea seed is shared with both seed enterprises and LSBs.
4. Improved grasspea demonstration plots are established and engagement events held with farmers.
5. Certified seed and QDS is produced to meet farmer demand.
6. Annual meeting where grasspea forecasting and production capacity is confirmed. New government purchase amount is set and LSBs are tasked with meeting a percentage of the overall improved grasspea capacity.
7. Government seed purchase reduces to 50% of total forecast demand for improved grasspea, with LSBs providing the other 50%

8. The initial LSBs double capacity and new grasspea-producing LSBs are established to meet demand.
9. Government cease purchase of improved grasspea seed from seed companies and seed is entirely supplied by LSBs

Key performance indicators to be included in addition to those mentioned in the previous scenarios:

- Percentage of total improved grasspea seed supplied by government and LSBs per year.
- Percentage of government-supplied *woredas* transitioned to LSBs as primary seed source.
- Number of coordination meetings held to monitor and communicate the transition pathway.
- Percent of MoA subsidy reduction per year.
- Farmer willingness increases to pay as subsidies decrease
- Percent of farmers reporting to switch to LSB seed, recorded each year.
- Percent of farmers reporting receiving seed without interruption despite supplier change for government to LSBs.
- Percentage of farmers reporting to continue to use improved grasspea through purchase from LSBs.
- Farmer satisfaction with suppliers and materials (government system and LSB).

Figure 6: The scenario three theory of change for a phased approach to improved grasspea seed delivery.

Conclusions

Grasspea is a crop with huge potential, but also one with major barriers for adoption of improved varieties. While the prevalence of grasspea production in Ethiopia is increasing and previous NISD research finds that farmers want varieties with greater resilience and yield traits, the low market value of the crop and informal and saved-seed approaches all pose challenges for the sustainable provision of improved grasspea varieties. Despite research breakthroughs to deliver safe and more productive grasspea varieties, comparatively little work has been done to identify viable and sustainable pathways to bring these innovations to Ethiopian farmers. Doing so could provide a safe, climate-smart crop for many rural Ethiopians across the country, and provide a model for other countries to trial. It is, however, essential to engage medical researchers and public health professionals in designing and implementing these interventions, to attempt to better understand the risk of neurotoxicity and to communicate with farmers about how to mitigate it.

Based on previous NISD research and the academic literature, this proposal has shared three potential scenarios for improved grasspea deployment and uptake. These include: (1) government-led seed purchase and distribution, (2) an integrated seed sector approach via Local Seed Businesses (LSBs) and; (3) a phased approach that starts with government distribution and transitions to LSB-led sustainable supply. These approaches were chosen and described based on their suitability for widespread and accessible grasspea deployment, and their fit within Ethiopian seed systems. While all three scenarios offer possible models for improved grasspea deployment, in this penultimate section, we critically reflect upon which approach we believe to have the greatest likelihood to succeed in supplying a sustainable source of improved grasspea varieties.

Scenario one offers a potentially straightforward method to quickly commission improved grasspea production by established seed producers. While a major critique of this government purchase approach is the inefficiency of the system (Hassena Beko, 2020), its use in this context seems likely to supply large volumes of improved grasspea to rural areas over short timeframes. This concern aside, the main challenge for the government purchase approach is its dependency on ongoing government investment for production and supply of grasspea seed. This approach poses a major challenge in convincing the MoA, given that the decision is not only for an initial investment, but one which is agreed

for the foreseeable future. Even if the present MoA leadership did agree to this system, changes to future budgets or shifts in political priorities could withdraw the investment. Should funding and support cease for any of these reasons, so too would the provision of improved grasspea with little other contingency. Scenario one therefore might provide a viable short-term shock response to quickly bulk and supply improved grasspea to rural areas, but would fail to empower local grasspea supply systems that bring durable and sustained production. Compared with the other scenarios, this approach seems the least likely to achieve long-term delivery of improved grasspea seed.

Both scenarios two and three address the sustainability challenge through the establishment of self-sustaining grassroots businesses trained in integrated seed systems practices. This same model is already working for around 25 other crops in the country, where the Ministry of Agriculture has worked with partners to establish over 240 LSBs (Borman et al., 2020). It is therefore plausible that LSBs exist across grasspea growing areas, that the model works in local contexts and that further LSB training could be extended to new farmer groups. The community nature of these approaches also makes them well placed to tailor grasspea communication and production to local consumers and producers. It also raises the likelihood of building trust with buyers, which is especially important given the safety concerns around grasspea. Linking these LSBs with research therefore offers further potential to link grasspea needs with researchers who can unlock these traits, and supply these varietal outputs to empower LSBs in reaching local users. Both scenario two and three do however rely on a number of assumptions for their sustained success. The first is that demand stimulation for improved grasspea will be sufficient to drive users to purchase improved grasspea varieties, and related to this, that LSBs will be motivated to continually produce improved grasspea seed. Similarly, the two-way model connecting LSBs and grasspea research depends on the ongoing investment from EIAR and other research actors to prioritise grasspea breeding and seed supply. The success of these approaches depends on the initial awareness building and demand creation methods, which vary between the two scenarios, with each having its costs and benefits.

Scenario two takes the standard integrated seed system approach to raise awareness for improved grasspea. It depends on the LSBs, with support from

DAS and researchers, to share the value of improved grasspea and multiply sufficient seed to supply it. The process stems from local exchange, predominantly between rural actors. While there are aforementioned benefits to this approach, there are also challenges in its potential efficacy and speed. The initial stages of improved grasspea production will likely pose the biggest challenge to build widespread demand creation, while also being the most critical stages for LSBs to determine the business sustainability of grasspea's production. Unlike other crops where there might be more varietal exchange and market potential, improved grasspea would be an entirely new product with unknown benefits. On one hand, this novelty combined with the increasing prevalence of grasspea production might drive curiosity to invest but on the other hand, it would be supplying a product where no previous awareness exists of the benefits. Convincing farmers to invest in and adopt the product might also prove challenging given that grasspea QDS is likely to retail for higher price than informally shared grasspea seed. While previous research suggests that farmers would be interested in improved varieties, there is a concern about there being sufficient and sustained demand, as well as willingness to pay, to make improved grasspea a viable product for LSBs. Achieving the initial local demand for grasspea is therefore crucial for the establishment and growth of the LSB models in scenario two and therefore requires careful coordination with LSBs and supporting actors. Scenario three however takes a different approach to this initial demand creation as an alternative pathway to build the demand that leads to a long-term demand and supply system.

Scenario three takes a combined approach, relying instead on the quick scale-up of government involvement to proliferate improved grasspea across rural areas as part of the demand initiation phase. Here, the system seeks to overcome the initial barrier of a lack of awareness for improved grasspea by widespread provision to farming groups, in collaboration with other partners encouraging adoption. Unlike scenario two, this approach would mean that actors across deployment areas are much more likely to have heard about and used improved grasspea before. This phased approach reduces the burden on LSBs to establish widespread demand and instead highlights them as key providers for an

emerging market. This model also means that the initial grasspea seed from government channels would be subsidised to reduce the financial barrier to the initial adoption. Doing so raises the likelihood of wider initial adoption, which is important as farmers' adoption decisions are often influenced by their neighbours and the prevalence of other actors adopting a new crop. For these reasons scenario three could offer the most promising approach as a result of the collaborative strengths of both the government and the LSB systems. This collaborative nature of scenario three is however also essential for the delivery of this system, and this requirement is also the main risk of this approach.

The first challenge is that scenario three requires the most actors, and therefore the most resources for this approach to initiate and implement. This might not only require greater investment, but also increased difficulty in coordinating the range of partners to start the approach and the continued communication to achieve the transition. This transition in particular will be complex in practice and likely variable across localities, preventing the likelihood of a one size fits all approach. For example, it is easy to imagine how external factors like ongoing political instability across many parts of rural Ethiopia could cause delays in communications or activities which have wider ramifications for how the government and integrated systems synchronise. Additionally, the transition from government purchase to LSB supply would need to be timed correctly in order to ensure that sufficient awareness and demand have been created and farmers are willing to pay for improved seed before LSBs take over. Overall, these concerns make scenario three a potentially costly and risky approach to deliver in practice.

Each of the three scenarios offers both advantages, and risks to achieving sustained delivery of improved grasspea varieties. Based on these considerations and our background research, we believe that scenario two provides the most promising approach combined with the greatest likelihood of successful delivery. We therefore conclude with an outline of suggested next steps to action the findings of this report, and implement an integrated seed systems approach for improved grasspea production in Ethiopia.

Scenario	Advantages	Disadvantages
Scenario 1: Government investment & distribution	<p>Rapid, large-scale seed delivery is possible, which is important for swift public health action to replace grasspea landraces.</p> <p>Potentially low financial barrier for farmers (depending on government subsidies/free provision).</p> <p>Draws on established distribution channels and farmer familiarity with these systems/</p>	<p>Sustainability concerns with ongoing reliance on government funding.</p> <p>Runs counter to Ethiopian policy direction to private sector led seed production and sales.</p> <p>Risk of inefficiencies and delays associated with previous use of these government seed systems.</p> <p>Potential limited reach to remote areas.</p> <p>More limited farmer choice and market responsiveness</p>
Scenario 2: Integrated seed system	<p>Can build on already established LSBs</p> <p>Most sustainable and self-sufficient option once established</p> <p>Provides farmers with lower costs for seed compared to formal seed companies</p> <p>Brings empowerment and capacity-building for local communities. Supports local seed systems.</p> <p>Builds a two-way feedback model between farmers and breeding that is responsive to local conditions</p> <p>Aligns with the current drive of Ethiopian policies</p>	<p>Complex stakeholder coordination required.</p> <p>Potential slow initial uptake and adoption by farmers, combined with potentially slow multiplication by LSBs.</p> <p>Initial financial investment needed for setup and training of new LSBs</p> <p>Potential challenges maintaining seed purity and consistent ODAP levels over time</p>
Scenario 3: Phased approach	<p>Combines strengths of rapid initial seed distribution (scenario 1) with long-term sustainability (scenario 2).</p> <p>Reduces initial pressure on LSBs to create widespread demand alone.</p> <p>Supports gradual market development with decreasing dependency on subsidies.</p> <p>Potentially more politically appealing than scenario 1 due to defined exit strategy for government funding.</p>	<p>Most complex scenario, bringing coordination and management challenges.</p> <p>Timing and logistics of transition between phases would be hard to estimate, difficult to implement and potentially different across locations.</p> <p>Risks during transition period of seed availability gaps or oversupply</p> <p>Requires ongoing close collaboration of partners over successive years to achieve adaptive management to unexpected changes.</p> <p>Potentially the highest initial resource requirements to establish.</p>

Recommendations for next steps

This report shares the authors' recommendations based on NISD research and the previous grasspea literature. This background research comes out of collaborations with some of the prominent research and collaborations for grasspea research, such as the Crop Trust, Fernand Lambien Trust, John Innes Centre and ICARDA, but more experts within and beyond grasspea research should be engaged to refine the proposed approach suggested in scenario two. We therefore suggest that the next immediate activities following this report should be the development of a day-long workshop centred on sharing, review and refinement of the suggested integrated model approach. The workshop objective would be to inform a detailed concept note, including partners, work packages and a timeline for project delivery. This workshop would also seek to build partnerships for the project, including actors who are embedded within Ethiopian agricultural and research bodies as potential project work package leads and delivery teams. A secondary objective of the workshop should identify a funding strategy for the proposal to support the full range of project activities as part of Ethiopian agricultural resilience planning. This should, for instance, identify both national and international budgets and donors interested in Ethiopian climate resilience planning, and develop an engagement plan to fund these activities.

Alongside this proposal, we suggest the workshop discussions be written up and synthesised with this business case document, to form (1) a detailed document for wider publication on pathways to

adoption of improved grasspea and (2) a focused evidence report to be presented to Ethiopian research and government. Both documents would provide useful resources for improved grasspea deployment across developing contexts and a model to achieve long-term provision and use of formally improved varieties for underutilised crops. This evidence report should also highlight the potential growing public health risk around existing grasspea production and uncertainty from farmers regarding toxicity risk and control. These factors are a policy concern in themselves and raise the urgency for action to replace existing grasspea landraces with safer varieties.

Outside of workshop activities, we recommend the more general engagement of grasspea research community with ESP and EOSA teams. This report notes several opportunities for grasspea research to bring new varieties to Ethiopian farmers, but a lack of existing collaboration with national agricultural farming and seed experts beyond EIAR. Generally encouraging more exchange between grasspea research and ESP and EOSA teams could improve understanding of the context of farming and developments across grasspea growing areas. Building this understanding could improve breeding targets for local needs and improve pathways for impact from research outputs.

More generally, the authors note several more general recommendations to encourage improved grasspea uptake. The first is that awareness of grasspea and its use in Ethiopia remains low, despite research

Grasspea Ethiopian business case report: Partner mapping improved varieties. The outcomes of this training could raise awareness around grasspea over rural areas, protect consumers and raise harvests.

Thirdly, EIAR is a gatekeeper for the improvement, testing and release of new grasspea varieties. There therefore need to be clear mechanisms to ensure EIAR's buy-in and commitment to grasspea improvement plans. This should be sought through engagement with EIAR management, and policy-level support to include grasspea in EIAR's strategic crops priorities.

Related to both of the previous points above, we suggest a general roll out of demonstration plots and pilot campaigns for farmers to try new grasspea varieties, and to stimulate markets for improved varieties. These marketing campaigns should tie in with connecting LSBs as key producers and highlight buyers, processors and retailers interested in grasspea products.

The authors believe the combined approach will further develop the model to bring improved grasspea to farmers' fields and encourage a long-term market for this nutritious climate-smart crop.

showing its consistent rise in production amongst farmers. We therefore call for a general step up in monitoring and communication around grasspea use and potential in Ethiopia to spread the word about this promising crop. This starts with greater recognition and measurement of grasspea yield estimates across Ethiopia, and the clearer reporting of these within government agricultural statistics. Communications activities should also seek to target wider legume researchers and breeders to raise awareness of the increasing volume of genetic and pre-breeding resources for grasspea. These new resources bring the potential for more comparable and targeted breeding strategies, inviting greater research for legume improvement. Communications activities should therefore be integrated as part of each of the grasspea deployment strategies suggested with this project. These communications could also target NGOs working to improve agricultural resilience across Ethiopia.

Secondly, DAs are consistently key players in each of the scenario plans. We therefore suggest training for DAs to equip them with knowledge on ODAP awareness and management, nutritional benefits of grasspea and effective agronomic practices for successful grasspea harvest and the potential of

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Partners' roles

Government

Ministry of Agriculture			
Federal national government department that oversees agricultural and rural development. Guides policy formulation and the practice of various other agricultural state-managed entities, including EIAR.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Prioritise grasspea as a crop for intervention; allocate budget for interventions; work with EIAR on the release of improved varieties; commission seed production from ESE and regional SEs; arrange for R/WBoAs to distribute grasspea seed; ensure farmers receive subsidised/free seed	Prioritise grasspea as a crop for intervention; request R/WBoAs to assign staff and DAs to support LSBs	Prioritise grasspea as a crop for intervention; allocate budget for interventions; work with EIAR on the release of improved varieties; commission seed production from ESE and regional SEs; arrange for R/WBoAs to distribute grasspea seed; ensure farmers receive subsidised/free seed; request R/WBoAs to assign staff and DAs to support LSBs
Enablers	Interest in improving farmers' harvests, livelihoods, nutrition, and climate resilience; already has a system in place for seed production and provision; able to produce low-cost seed through public seed enterprises	Interest in improving farmers' harvests, livelihoods, nutrition, and climate resilience; scenario requires little budget and input from ministry; supports transition away from public sector-dominated seed provision.	Interest in improving farmers' harvests, livelihoods, nutrition, and climate resilience; scenario requires less budget and input than scenario 1; supports eventual transition away from public sector-dominated seed provision;
Constraints	Limited budgets for subsidised/free seed; newer strategy for transition to private sector-led seed production and sales; prioritises other crops for staple foods (wheat, maize, tef) and exports (coffee, chickpea, sesame, livestock); concerns over promoting a crop with potential public health implications	May prefer LSBs to focus on seed of more widely consumed crops; concerns over promoting a crop with potential public health implications	High budget required in first phase; concerns over potential lag time for LSBs to be ready, lengthening MoA's involvement; may prefer to focus on seed of more widely consumed crops; concerns over promoting a crop with potential public health implications
Regional & Woreda BoAs (R/WBoAs)			
In charge of regional and district agricultural activities according to local potential and needs. Organise local actors and DAs to serve farmers and rural communities.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Prioritise grasspea as a crop for intervention; allocate budgets for interventions; identify grasspea growing <i>woredas</i> and work with other partners to design interventions; work with regional SEs to receive seed; calculate demand and distribute seed to farmers; organise awareness creation and promotional events; gather farmer feedback and communicate to RARIs	Prioritise grasspea as a crop for intervention; identify grasspea growing <i>woredas</i> and support project design; organise awareness creation and promotional events; assign staff and DAs to support LSBs and farmers; assist with demand calculation and gathering and communicating feedback to RARIs	Prioritise grasspea as a crop for intervention; allocate budgets for interventions; identify grasspea growing <i>woredas</i> and work with other partners to design interventions; work with RSEs to receive seed; calculate demand and distribute seed to farmers; organise awareness creation and promotional events; gather farmer feedback and communicate to RARIs; assign staff and DAs to support LSBs and farmers; assist with demand calculation and gathering and communicating feedback to RARIs

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Enablers	Implements activities to achieve shared goals of improving farmers' harvests, livelihoods, nutrition, and climate resilience; already has a system in place for seed distribution and relationships with regional SEs; understands local farmers opportunities, needs and challenges	May support transition to LSB seed provision to free up own capacity for other activities	Implements activities to achieve shared goals of improving farmers' harvests, livelihoods, nutrition, and climate resilience; already has a system in place for seed distribution and relationships with regional SEs; understands local farmers opportunities, needs and challenges; may support transition to LSB seed provision to free up own capacity for other activities
Constraints	Needs MoA signal to launch grasspea activities; possible budget and staffing limitations to undertake seed distribution for new crop; may choose to prioritise locally important food or cash crops; DAs may require additional training to support farmers with grasspea production	Supporting LSBs with DA time and promotional events may take time and budgets away from other activities; DAs may require additional training to support farmers with grasspea production	Needs MoA signal to launch grasspea activities; possible budget and staffing limitations to undertake seed distribution for new crop; may choose to prioritise locally important food or cash crops; concerns over potential lag time for LSBs to be ready, lengthening R/WBoAs' involvement; DAs may require additional training to support farmers with grasspea production

Ethiopian Agricultural Authority (EAA)

EAA is a federal authority that ensures the appropriate standardisation, registration, and operation of agricultural technologies, inputs, products and services. It carries out inspections to ensure that they comply with performance, quality, health and safety standards.

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Carry out seed inspection and certification to ensure quality; develop standards for grasspea seed quality	Carry out seed inspection and declare QDS; develop standards for grasspea seed quality	Carry out seed inspection and certification to ensure quality or declare QDS; develop standards for grasspea seed quality
Enabler	Likely to have a working relationship with MoA and R/WBoAs to facilitate smooth action	QDS follows a less stringent process than formal certification and may be less resource-intensive	Likely to have a working relationship with MoA and R/WBoAs to facilitate smooth action; QDS follows a less stringent process than formal certification and may be less resource-intensive
Constraint	As a relatively new institution set up in 2021, it may have limited staff, budget, and capacity for large scale inspections; as a lower priority crop, EAA may lack technical capacity to inspect grasspea seed	As a relatively new institution set up in 2021, it may have limited staff, budget, and capacity for large scale inspections; as a lower priority crop, EAA may lack technical capacity to inspect grasspea seed; may need to set up new working parameters with LSBs	As a relatively new institution set up in 2021, it may have limited staff, budget, and capacity for large scale inspections; as a lower priority crop, EAA may lack technical capacity to inspect grasspea seed; may need to set up new working parameters with LSBs

Research

Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) & national research centres			
Oversees running of national research centres across the country, coordinates agricultural research countrywide, and advises the Ethiopian government on agricultural research policy. EIAR also supports capacity building of farmers, DAs, researchers, and others.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Works with MoA on the promotion Wasie seed variety; works with international research institutes to introduce other improved varieties; gathers input from RARIs and RBoAs on varietal performance and desired characteristics for future breeding	Works with MoA on the promotion Wasie seed variety; works with international research institutes to introduce other improved varieties; gathers input from RARIs, RBoAs and LSBs on varietal performance and desired characteristics for future breeding	Works with MoA on the promotion Wasie seed variety; works with international research institutes to introduce other improved varieties; gathers input from RARIs RBoAs and LSBs on varietal performance and desired characteristics for future breeding
Enablers	Has already researched and approved release of Wasie variety; works closely with ICARDA; has working relationship with ESE	Has already researched and approved release of Wasie variety; works closely with ICARDA;	Has already researched and approved release of Wasie variety; works closely with ICARDA; has working relationship with ESE
Constraints	Possible budget and staffing limitations to undertake research on new varieties; may prioritise food and commercial crops over grasspea; may perceive too little farmer and consumer demand for grasspea, which may be why Wasie is not widely used/promoted	Possible budget and staffing limitations to undertake research on new varieties; may prioritise food and commercial crops over grasspea; may perceive too little farmer and consumer demand for grasspea, which may be why Wasie is not widely used/promoted	Possible budget and staffing limitations to undertake research on new varieties; may prioritise food and commercial crops over grasspea; may perceive too little farmer and consumer demand for grasspea, which may be why Wasie is not widely used/promoted
Regional Agricultural Research Institutes (RARIs)			
Research institutes located in the four major regions of the country (Oromia, Amhara, Tigray and SNNP) focusing on localized research topics and administered by the regional governments.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Work with DAs to identify local grasspea growing conditions and desired traits; help promote improved varieties; work with RSEs to ensure production of improved varieties; compile farmer feedback and feed to EIAR and ICARDA	Work with DAs to identify local grasspea growing conditions and desired traits; help promote improved varieties; work with LSBs on production of improved varieties; compile farmer feedback and feed to EIAR and ICARDA	Work with DAs to identify local grasspea growing conditions and desired traits; help promote improved varieties; work with RSEs and LSBs on production of improved varieties; compile farmer feedback and feed to EIAR and ICARDA
Enabler	Familiarity with local farming conditions and farmer practices; established relationship with RSEs; established relationship with some international research institutes	Familiarity with local farming conditions and farmer practices; established relationship with some international research institutes	Familiarity with local farming conditions and farmer practices; established relationship with RSEs; established relationship with some international research institutes
Constraint	Unlikely to have done research on grasspea and may lack technical capacity; budget limitations; length of time between getting farmer feedback and producing desired varieties	Unlikely to have done research on grasspea and may lack technical capacity; may not have working relationship with LSBs; budget limitations; length of time between getting farmer feedback and producing desired varieties	Unlikely to have done research on grasspea and may lack technical capacity; may not have working relationship with LSBs; budget limitations; length of time between getting farmer feedback and producing desired varieties

International research institutes (ICARDA, JIC)

ICARDA is an international institute and part of the CGIAR system. ICARDA's work in Ethiopia focuses on biodiversity, crops and livestock, development of seed systems, water and land management, and capacity development. ICARDA works with EIAR, RARIs, MoA, RBoAS, public seed enterprises and seed producer cooperatives.

JIC is an independent, international centre of excellence in plant science, genetics and microbiology based in the UK. JIC has conducted research to produce low and zero toxin grasspea varieties. JIC also led the release of the most complete grasspea genome sequence, and sequenced the grasspea diversity held at the ICARDA genebank.

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Provide Ethiopian research institutes with improved grasspea seed varieties; train ESE and RSEs on grasspea seed production; incorporate feedback from farmers on varietal performance and desired traits for future research and breeding	Provide Ethiopian research institutes with improved grasspea seed varieties; train LSB on quality grasspea seed production; incorporate feedback from farmers on varietal performance and desired traits for future research and breeding	Provide Ethiopian research institutes with improved grasspea seed varieties; train ESE and RSEs on grasspea seed production; incorporate feedback from farmers on varietal performance and desired traits for future research and breeding
Enablers	Focused on producing improved, low-toxin grasspea varieties; can draw upon lessons from interventions in other countries; ICARDA has a relationship with Ethiopian research institutes	Focused on producing improved, low-toxin grasspea varieties; can draw upon lessons from interventions in other countries; ICARDA has a relationship with Ethiopian research institutes	Focused on producing improved, low-toxin grasspea varieties; can draw upon lessons from interventions in other countries; ICARDA has a relationship with Ethiopian research institutes
Constraints	Must have the buy-in of Ethiopian government institutes to work on grasspea interventions; will require funding for future phases of research; length of time between getting farmer feedback and producing desired varieties	Must have the buy-in of Ethiopian government institutes to work on grasspea interventions; will require funding for future phases of research; length of time between getting farmer feedback and producing desired varieties	Must have the buy-in of Ethiopian government institutes to work on grasspea interventions; will require funding for future phases of research; length of time between getting farmer feedback and producing desired varieties

Seed producers

Ethiopian Seed Enterprise (ESE) and Regional Seed Enterprises (RSEs)			
ESE is a state owned company overseen by MoA that is the largest seed supplier in Ethiopia. It runs various production sites in the major regions of Oromia, Amhara, and SNNP.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Work with research institutes to produce improved grasspea seed; work with R/WBoAs to deliver seed to intervention areas;	Work with research institutes to produce improved grasspea seed; work with R/WBoAs to deliver seed to LSBs in intervention areas; support LSBs to enhance their capacity to produce grasspea seed	Work with research institutes to produce improved grasspea seed; work with R/WBoAs to deliver seed to LSBs in intervention areas; support LSBs to enhance their capacity to produce grasspea seed
Enablers	Capable of producing seed at scale; established relationship with MoA and RBoAs; incentivised by guaranteed market for seed produced	Capable of producing seed at scale;	Capable of producing seed at scale; established relationship with MoA and RBoAs; incentivised by guaranteed market for seed produced
Constraints	May prefer to produce seeds for staple, export, or commercial viable crops as government purchase price may be low; may need capacity building to produce grasspea seed	May prefer to produce seeds for staple, export, or commercial viable crops; may need capacity building to produce grasspea seed – conversely, may see LSBs as competition if farmer demand for seed is high and grasspea is commercially viable	May prefer to produce seeds for staple, export, or commercial viable crops as government purchase price may be low – conversely, may see LSBs as competition if farmer demand for seed is high and grasspea is commercially viable; may need capacity building to produce grasspea seed
Local Seed Businesses (LSB)			
Small- and medium-sized seed businesses, often owned and operated by farmers. They serve the community by producing seed for locally grown crops.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	<i>LSBs are not involved in this scenario</i>	Produce improved grasspea seed and distribute to farmers; organise promotional and awareness creation events; work with DAs to calculate demand; gather feedback from farmers and varietal performance and desired characteristics	Produce improved grasspea seed and distribute to farmers; organise promotional and awareness creation events; work with DAs to calculate demand; gather feedback from farmers and varietal performance and desired characteristics
Enabler	N/A	Familiarity with local farmers' needs and challenges; receive support from R/WBoAs, research institutes and conveners to enhance seed production capacity; opportunity to gain new skills; opportunity for new revenue stream	Demand is sufficiently established by government purchase approach; familiarity with local farmers' needs and challenges; receive support from R/WBoAs, research institutes and conveners to enhance seed production capacity; opportunity to gain new skills; opportunity for new revenue stream
Constraint	N/A	Perceived or lack of demand to purchase seed; possible capacity limitation to produce seed; possible capacity limitation to meet quality standards	Perceived or lack of demand to purchase seed; possible capacity limitation to produce seed; possible capacity limitation to meet quality standards; improperly timed transition could lead to LSBs producing too little or too much seed

Conveners

Ethiopian Seed Partnership (ESP)			
<p>ESP aims to improve smallholder farmers' food security, nutrition, and resilience by giving them better access to quality seed varieties. ESP helps to develop private sector capacity for seed production and expands into areas affected by drought and conflict. One component of the partnership's work is to build farmer- and community-based seed system capacity.</p>			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Advocate for MoA and EIAR to prioritise grasspea in their operations; facilitate knowledge sharing between research and implementation actors; lead in the design of grasspea interventions; help organise promotional and awareness creation events; support with fundraising for new initiatives	Advocate for MoA and EIAR to prioritise grasspea in their operations; facilitate knowledge sharing between research and implementation actors; lead in the design of grasspea interventions; help organise promotional and awareness creation events; build the capacity of LSBs to produce grasspea seed; support with fundraising for new initiatives	Advocate for MoA and EIAR to prioritise grasspea in their operations; facilitate knowledge sharing between research and implementation actors; lead in the design of grasspea interventions; help organise promotional and awareness creation events; build the capacity of LSBs to produce grasspea seed; support with fundraising for new initiatives
Enablers	Recognises the potential of grasspea for food security, nutrition, and resilience; established relationships with key sector actors;	Recognises the potential of grasspea for food security, nutrition, and resilience; established relationships with key sector actors; already promoting ISSD model and can draw examples from other countries; has already set up and capacitated several LSBs	Recognises the potential of grasspea for food security, nutrition, and resilience; established relationships with key sector actors; already promoting ISSD model and can draw examples from other countries; has already set up and capacitated several LSBs
Constraints	Possibly limited influence on MoA priority setting; facilitation role limits what they can do (versus direct implementation)	Possibly limited influence on MoA priority setting; facilitation role limits what they can do (versus direct implementation)	Possibly limited influence on MoA priority setting; facilitation role limits what they can do (versus direct implementation)
EOSA			
<p>EOSA leads the training of LSBs in the production of quality declared grasspea seed, supports initial seed production cycles, and facilitates linkages between LSBs, researchers, and extension agents. Also plays a key role in promoting awareness of improved grasspea seed and supporting demonstration events.</p>			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	<i>EOSA are not involved in this scenario</i>	EOSA leads the training of LSBs in the production of quality declared grasspea seed, supports initial seed production cycles, and facilitates linkages between LSBs, researchers, and DAs. Also promotes awareness of improved grasspea seed and supporting demonstration events.	EOSA leads the training of LSBs in the production of quality declared grasspea seed, supports initial seed production cycles, and facilitates linkages between LSBs, researchers, and DAs. Also promotes awareness of improved grasspea seed and supporting demonstration events.
Enabler	N/A	Extensive experience in farmer training and seed system development; established partnerships with ESP, extension agents, and research institutes; operational familiarity with QDS processes; credibility among local seed actors.	Extensive experience in farmer training and seed system development; established partnerships with ESP, extension agents, and research institutes; operational familiarity with QDS processes; credibility among local seed actors.
Constraint	N/A	Relies on collaboration with multiple actors (e.g., EIAR, extension services) for effective implementation; may face resource limitations for sustained engagement across expanding LSBs.	Same as scenario 2, plus might face difficulty in the complex task of communicating and coordinating scale up and training of LSB activities around the transition phase.

Local actors

Processors & buyers			
Processors, called <i>baltena</i> , are local businesses making a variety of traditional food items for sale. Other buyers may purchase grasspea crop from farmers for sale elsewhere.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Take part in promotional and awareness creation events to understand opportunities; attend trainings on proper grasspea preparation to remove toxin; prepare a variety of grasspea food items to demonstrate potential; assess consumer demand for grasspea and share with DAs, farmers, and other actors	Take part in promotional and awareness creation events to understand opportunities; attend trainings on proper grasspea preparation to remove toxin; prepare a variety of grasspea food items to demonstrate potential; assess consumer demand for grasspea and share with DAs, farmers, and other actors	Take part in promotional and awareness creation events to understand opportunities; attend trainings on proper grasspea preparation to remove toxin; prepare a variety of grasspea food items to demonstrate potential; assess consumer demand for grasspea and share with DAs, farmers, and other actors
Enablers	Interface with consumers provides insight into demand and preferences; potential additional revenue stream; government subsidised or free seed may lower farmers' selling price for grasspea	Interface with consumers provides insight into demand and preferences; potential additional revenue stream	Interface with consumers provides insight into demand and preferences; potential additional revenue stream; government subsidised or free seed may lower farmers' selling price for grasspea
Constraints	Consumer demand may be low, especially with concerns about neurotoxicity, and processors and buyers may have to organise their own promotions	Consumer demand may be low, especially with concerns about neurotoxicity, and processors and buyers may have to organise their own promotions; farmers may charge more for crop if produced with seed bought (rather than subsidised or free)	Consumer demand may be low, especially with concerns about neurotoxicity, and processors and buyers may have to organise their own promotions; farmer prices for grasspea crop may go up after transitioning to buying seed from LSBs
Farmers			
Farmers currently growing or with the potential to grow grasspea in selected intervention areas.			
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Role	Take part in promotional and awareness creation events to understand grasspea opportunities; take part in trainings on grasspea growing and processing; receive subsidised or free improved seed from WBoAs; cultivate grasspea crops, gathering information on performance and desirable traits; provide feedback to R/WBoAs through DAs; engage with processors and buyers to assess consumer demand for grasspea crops	Take part in promotional and awareness creation events to understand grasspea opportunities; take part in trainings on grasspea growing and processing; buy improved seed from LSBs; cultivate grasspea crops, gathering information on performance and desirable traits; provide feedback to R/WBoAs through DAs; engage with processors and buyers to assess consumer demand for grasspea crops	Take part in promotional and awareness creation events to understand grasspea opportunities; take part in trainings on grasspea growing and processing; receive subsidised or free seed from WBoAs, then transition to buying improved seed from LSBs; cultivate grasspea crops, gathering information on performance and desirable traits; provide feedback to R/WBoAs through DAs; engage with processors and buyers to assess consumer demand for grasspea crops
Enabler	Awareness creation events help farmers see opportunities; improved seed may perform better than farmer produced seed; government purchased seed is subsidised or free; government channels are familiar; chance to influence grasspea breeding through their feedback	Awareness creation events help farmers see opportunities; improved seed may perform better than farmer produced seed; LSBs may be more efficient at providing seed in the right quantities; chance to influence grasspea breeding through their feedback	Awareness creation events help farmers see opportunities; improved seed may perform better than farmer produced seed; chance to test viability of grasspea through subsidised/free seed before buying; chance to influence grasspea breeding through their feedback

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Constraint	Government seed channels may be inefficient and may not provide the right quantities; concerns over neurolathyrism may not be overcome by grasspea's positive attributes	Farmers may not be willing to pay for seed – conversely, LSBs may not produce sufficient seed to meet farmer demand; concerns over neurolathyrism may not be overcome by grasspea's positive attributes	Government seed channels may be inefficient but LSBs may not produce sufficient seed; farmers may be unwilling to pay for seed from LSBs that they received for free or subsidised from government channels; concerns over neurolathyrism may not be overcome by grasspea's positive attributes

The NISD is a partnership between

